

D2.7: Final Stakeholder Map

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Abstract:

This document is the final version of the initial Deliverable 2.1, whose objective is to scope the wide field of potential stakeholders, to determine who is affected and need to affect the European Open Science Cloud and to organize and manage the involvement of these stakeholders. The deliverable provides a mapping of the stakeholder landscape which is based both on desk research and on stakeholder feedback.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the final version of the initial Deliverable 2.1, whose objective is to scope the wide field of potential stakeholders, to determine who is affected and need to affect the European Open Science Cloud and to organize and manage the involvement of these stakeholders. The deliverable provides a mapping of the stakeholder landscape which is based both on desk research and on stakeholder feedback. The objectives of the deliverable are the following:

- To define the roles of stakeholders in EOSC.
- To describe the types of stakeholders.
- To present the methodology for making the final mapping of stakeholders.
- To present the feedback of stakeholders.

The deliverable presents a methodology for scoping the stakeholders based on desk research and interviews with key stakeholders. In Section 2, we describe the methodology and the stakeholder roles, and in Section 3 the main types of stakeholders that we have identified. In Section 4, we present the main e-infrastructures, which we consider as a basic starting point for mapping the stakeholder landscape. In Section 5, we go a step forward by exploring all the organizations that participated in Horizon 2020 infrastructure projects (both e-infrastructures and Research Infrastructure projects) and in FP7 infrastructure projects. Our analysis is based on the number of participations of each organization in the infrastructure projects. We present our results by activity type and also by a member state. Moreover, in Section 6 we categorize RIs according to their scientific domain. In Section 7, we present the feedback we received from stakeholders through various channels, and finally Section 7 concludes the deliverable by highlighting the basic results.

2 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this deliverable is to provide an evidence based scoping document regarding the relevant EOSC stakeholders.

The document contains a comprehensive methodological approach, a presentation of the core assumptions behind the choice of different types of stakeholders and the validation approach adopted in order to verify the validity of the empirical data collected in the course of materialisation of the deliverable related to this Work Package.

2.1 Approach and Methodology

2.1.1 An objectives driven approach

An exercise of scoping and mapping of the stakeholders involved in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) presupposes an understanding of the broader context and ecosystem of European policies and initiatives in which EOSC is placed. Such an understanding is crucial for establishing a methodology that will both identify the stakeholders that are relevant for the EOSC's governance model and set the foundations for an inquiry on the role that such stakeholders should have in the EOSC governance system. EOSC is a crucial part of the broader cloud policy in Europe, that is the European Cloud Initiative (ECI),¹ an initiative that aims at building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe. At the heart of this initiative is an understanding of digital science as a core element of the European development policies and the establishment of open science² as a critical driver for the data economy in Europe. Following an approach that mirrors the Open Data³ policies in the context of eGovernment⁴ which views data⁵ as the oil of the digital economy, the European Cloud Initiative places the free flow of data, scientific results and knowledge at the heart of the research and innovation process.

Such policies not only reinforce a broader policy design that views research as a crucial developmental element, being one of the three poles of the triple helix of smart specialization,⁶ the other two being the public and the private sector but goes even further: it places research and scientific capacity, both in terms of infrastructures and human capital as the centre of Europe's industrial policies on the 4th industrial revolution.⁷

¹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: European Cloud Initiative – Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe, Brussels, 19.4.2016 COM(2016) 178 final <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0178&from=EN>

² See e.g. Research and Innovation (2014) Validation of the results of the public consultation on Science 2.0: Science in Transition <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/news/final-report-science-20-public-consultation>

³ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Open data An engine for innovation, growth and transparent governance Brussels, 12.12.2011 COM(2011) 882 final <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2011:0882:FIN:EN:PDF>

⁴ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: EU eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020 Accelerating the digital transformation of government Brussels, 19.4.2016 COM(2016) 179 final <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0179&from=EN>

⁵ See also European Commission, DG CONNECT/ Unit G3 - Data Value Chain (2013) Elements of a Data Value Chain http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=3488

⁶ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Regional Policy contributing to smart growth in Europe 2020 Brussels, 6.10.2010 COM(2010) 553 final http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docoffic/official/communic/smart_growth/comm2010_553_en.pdf

⁷ These are included in the Digitising European Industry strategy as expressed in the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Digitising European Industry

Moreover, it is essential to achieve the right scale of the technologies that are the necessary substratum of the European Digital Market: "The industrial revolution of our time is digital. We need the right scale for technologies such as cloud computing, data-driven science and the internet of things to reach their full potential. As companies aim to scale up across the Single Market, public e-services should also meet today's needs: be digital, open and cross-border by design. The EU is the right scale for the digital times."⁸ The objective of such a pan-European cloud is to give Europe's 1.7 million researchers and 70 million science and technology professionals⁹ a virtual environment to store, manage, analyse and re-use a significant amount of research data.

EOSC, should thus be seen not merely as a key component of the European Research Area (ERA) policies¹⁰ that aims at supporting seamless open access to a wide range of digital science services across the European Union for all researchers and scientists, but also as an equally important part of the industrial, commercial and developmental policies of Europe.¹¹ Accordingly, the stakeholders involved in EOSC cannot be isolated from the broader context of the players that are to be affected and will use EOSC. These need to include key commercial players, governments and citizens as well as the research and scientific community that have to continue unhindered and further advance its work, i.e. research. In other words, we should identify stakeholders both from the supply and demand sides of the cloud related services ecosystem. At the same time, we also need to always bear in mind that albeit its impact for commerce, the public sector and the citizen, EOSC has science and the relevant research and e-infrastructures as its starting point and core constituency.

The European Commission and the organizations signing the EOSC Declaration¹² have made stated that the support the implementation of EOSC as "a federation of existing and planned research data infrastructures, adding a soft overlay to connect them and making them operate as one seamless European research data infrastructure". This fact renders are obvious stakeholders all existing EU and national infrastructures, and the entities that implement them. This renders the statistical analysis we present on FP7 and H2020 infrastructure projects in Sections 5 and 6, extremely relevant.

Understanding the stakeholder landscape is a crucial task for an active stakeholder engagement and also for creating objective and transparent criteria for selection and involvement of Member States and Associated Countries representatives and stakeholders, such as the large pan-European research infrastructures (RIs), public research organizations (PROs) and Universities in the Executive Board, working groups/subgroups and other relevant committees;

Reaping the full benefits of a Digital Single Market (COM(2016) 180 final) <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0180>

⁸ Andrius Ansip, European Commission Press Release "Delivering on its Strategy to create a Digital Single Market, the Commission today unveiled its plans to help European industry, SMEs, researchers and public authorities make the most of new technologies."

⁹ Supra note 1, pg.6 "The European Open Science Cloud aims to give Europe a global lead in scientific data infrastructures, to ensure that European scientists reap the full benefits of data-driven science. Practically, it will offer 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science and technology a virtual environment with free at the point of use, open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines."

¹⁰ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth Brussels, 17.7.2012 COM(2012) 392 final http://ec.europa.eu/research/era/pdf/era-communication/era-communication_en.pdf

¹¹ Indicatively, see the EOSC description at the Digital Single Market web page: "The European Commission launched the European Cloud Initiative to capitalise on the data revolution. It will provide European science, industry and public authorities with world-class digital infrastructure that bring state of the art computing and data storage capacity to the fingertips of any scientists and engineer in the European Union." <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-open-science-cloud#Article>

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/eosc_declaration.pdf

2.1.2 Methodological Directions

The starting point for the task of identifying the relevant stakeholders is the European Research Infrastructures (RIs),¹³ a core horizontal part of which are the e-Infrastructures.¹⁴ E-Infrastructures or Digital Infrastructures constitute the backbone of the European research and a prerequisite for sustainable innovation and growth. Two of the most essential components of the European Cloud Initiative, EOSC and the European Data Infrastructure (EDI),¹⁵ built upon existing e-Infrastructures, operate in conjunction with most European Research Infrastructures and relate to key Digital Single Market initiatives¹⁶.

Hence, we start our investigation by providing an initial analysis with regards to the different players at different layers of the e-infrastructure stack. These layers, as expressed in the EC Communication on the European Cloud Initiative and the European Data Infrastructure, may be simply summarized in: (a) the data infrastructures which store and manage data (including scholarly communication infrastructures and services); (b) the high-bandwidth networks which transport data; and (c) the ever more powerful computers which can be used to process the data.¹⁷

¹³ “Research infrastructures are facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. Where relevant, they may be used beyond research, e.g. for education or public services. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments); knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives or scientific data; e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks; and any other infrastructure of a unique nature essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. Such infrastructures may be 'single-sited', 'virtual' or 'distributed'.” Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2014-2015 - 4. European Research Infrastructures http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/main/h2020-wp1415-infrastructures_en.pdf; See also HORIZON 2020 - Work Programme 2016 - 2017 European Research Infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures) http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2016_2017/main/h2020-wp1617-infrastructures_en.pdf “The Research Infrastructures Work Programme 2016-2017 will put wide emphasis on fostering the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures (including through the optimisation of assessment and evaluation procedures), on expanding the role and impact of research infrastructures in the innovation chain and on maximising the exploitation of data produced and/or collected by research infrastructures.”

¹⁴ E-Infrastructures are Information and Communication Technologies infrastructures. According to HORIZON 2020 - Work Programme 2016 – 2017 The e-infrastructures call for 2016/2017 will support the European policies on open research data, data and computing intensive science, research and education networking, highperformance computing and big data innovation.

¹⁵ “The European Data Infrastructure is one of the three pillars of the European Cloud initiative - Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe. By combing world-class supercomputing capability with high-speed connectivity and leading-edge data and software services for science, industry and the public sector, the European Data infrastructure will allow fully unlocking the value of big data.” DG CONNECT Glossary <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/glossary#europeandatainfrastructure>. See also supra note 1, p. 3 “[The European Cloud Initiative] aims to deploy the underpinning super-computing capacity, the fast connectivity and the high-capacity cloud solutions they need via a European Data Infrastructure.”

¹⁶ “The European Cloud Initiative builds on the achievements of the European Cloud Strategy and the High Performance Computing (HPC) Strategy. It will build on initiatives such as the recently announced Important Project of Common European Interest (IPCEI) on HPC and Big Data enabled applications. It takes forward the policy developed in the Communication on Big Data and supports the European Open Science policy agenda which aims to increase the quality and impact of science, building on the achievements of Open Access.” Supra note 1, p.3

¹⁷ “The Cloud can be understood as the combination of three interdependent elements: the data infrastructures which store and manage data; the high-bandwidth networks which transport data; and the ever more powerful computers which can be used to process the data. The ability to analyse and exploit this Big Data is having an impact on the global economy and society, opening up the possibility of major industrial and social innovations. A key part of this impact is the change in the way scientific research is carried out, as we move rapidly towards Open Science.” Supra note 1, p.2.

Each one of the key existing e-infrastructures gathers a series of stakeholders that contribute to the realisation of different –and sometimes multiple- layers of the cloud stack. Some of the stakeholders participating in these e-infrastructures may operate as service/ data providers and some as consumers. More frequently than not, they will play both roles simultaneously for different aspects of their operation. The European RIs and e-Infrastructures certainly do not exhaust the range of EOOSC stakeholders but provide the first cycle of players that are involved in the development, provision and consumption of Open Science related cloud services. Thus, the first stage (Stage 1A) of our investigation focuses on understanding the number and kind of stakeholders participating in European RIs and e-Infrastructures as well as the nature of their participation. For that purpose, we have compiled a data-set of all RIs and e-Infrastructures and have embarked into a study of:

- The kind of institutions participating
 - o Research Institutions
 - o Higher Education Institutions
 - o Funders
 - o Policy Makers
 - o Private Sector
 - o Other
- The number of participants per Member State (MS)
- The different RIs and e-Infrastructures in which each of these institutions participates
- The way in which these institutions participate (i.e. role in the consortium)
- Whether these institutions participate as users or consumers of such services.

Such an approach is both quantitative and qualitative: It focuses on the range (no. of Infrastructures per Member State) and intensity of participation (no. of institutions per Infrastructure/ no. of infrastructure a specific organisation participates to) in order to identify the top participants per MS.

In parallel (Stage 1B), we focus on e-Infrastructures in order to get more detailed information regarding the participation of different institutions there. More specifically, we focus on the following e-Infrastructures:

- EGI
- EUDAT
- GEANT
- OpenAIRE
- PRACE

In these e-infrastructures we explore their positioning in the EOOSC, their legal and institutional form, their governance models and analyse the mechanisms of interaction both with their partners and third parties. A similar approach is adopted for the analysis of mature RIs, as assessed by the latest ESFRI ¹⁸ (Stage 1C). In the second stage of our analysis we return to representative institutions that cover diverse roles in the EOOSC ecosystem, in order to get more qualitative information. We reach out to selected stakeholders, particularly policy makers, open science RIs and funders, as well as other strategic players at the Member State level, which are at the forefront of the open science landscape and could provide us with useful insight with regards to the implementation of the EOOSC related policies at the MS level (Stage 2C).

¹⁸ See http://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index_en.cfm?pg=esfri

Through detailed questionnaires and occasionally semi-structured interviews of key stakeholders we identify the following elements: (a) their awareness about EOOSC, (b) their predisposition towards FAIR principles and (c) their expectations from EOOSC.

The positioning of such stakeholders within the broader context of the European Research Area, is –in turn– closely related to the Digital Single Market¹⁹ policies in Europe.

The key elements of the adopted methodology may be summarised as follows:

- Understanding the scope and objectives of EOOSC: these are derived from formal EC papers and particularly the European Research Policies
- Range of infrastructures and services
- European policy initiatives and projects
- Desk research
- Identification of key stakeholders for focused interviews
- Commercial players and the EU value chain

¹⁹ See https://ec.europa.eu/commission/priorities/digital-single-market_en

3 STAKEHOLDER TYPES

EOSC will offer services to the whole research community and every participant or supporting entity of the research community could be considered as a stakeholder. To promote an efficient governance scheme, we need to categorize them and emphasize on the most influential ones. The governance scheme should be flexible but at the same time inclusive. Engaging already organized communities, organizations and other infrastructures is a suitable starting point in identifying the most important stakeholders of EOSC. We have categorized the most prominent stakeholders into the following groups:

- **European e-Infrastructures:** Existing key European e-Infrastructures (EGI, EUDAT, GEANT, OpenAIRE, and PRACE) are the natural starting point for engaging EOSC stakeholders. They represent activities that are closely linked to e-Infrastructures, including cloud operations, and they are already organized in for further integration.
- **Data/Research Initiatives:** There is a variety of organizations and initiatives, e.g., RDA interest²⁰ and working groups²¹, which constitute already organized research communities with specific stakes in cloud services.
- **Cloud providers.** Cloud services providers, public and private, are critical stakeholders by definition in EOSCPilot. Engaging major companies, e.g., Amazon, that provide services to a wide range of research activities is essential for bringing together the needs of the research communities and the offered services, and to address some Data privacy issues.
- **Research funders.** Funding bodies both on national and EU level are major stakeholder in EOSC, since they support research in all its stages. Despite their different organizational schemes in different countries, EOSC needs to actively engage them in supporting the future direction of EU cloud infrastructures.
- **Cloud community.** The research community working with cloud technologies and participating in EU cloud projects is a valuable ally in designing the framework for cloud services in EU. Identifying key players in this sector is a significant challenge.
- **Research Communities and Institutions.** Researchers, Research communities and Research institutions as main consumers of cloud services are a primary pillar in EOSC, since they define the consumer side of the cloud ecosystem. This is a broad class of consumers and identifying the key contact points and the right organization scheme to engage them is a complex task. Some of them are already organized at European scale, such as the HPC Centre of Excellence (CoEs)²².
- **Research Infrastructures (RIs).** The Research Infrastructure projects of EC complement the existing EU infrastructure landscape, by providing thematic (vertical) infrastructures in contrast with the horizontal e-infrastructure. RIs are the key starting point for engaging communities since they are already organized in an operational structure and use or provide cloud services.
- **Policy makers.** Policy makers affect cloud infrastructures in profound ways, even when they do not act as funders. For example, regulatory bodies on data privacy, on competition and of course on research can shape the future of the cloud ecosystem in the EU. EOSCPilot has to identify the most closely related ones and investigate the more productive way to engage them.

²⁰ See <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/interest-groups>

²¹ See <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/working-groups>

²² See <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/news/eight-new-centres-excellence-computing-applications>

4 E-INFRASTRUCTURES

In this Section we examine in more detail the main e-Infrastructures, i.e., EGI, EUDAT, GEANT, OpenAIRE, and PRACE as we consider them a basic starting point for identifying the main stakeholders and governance models for EOSC.

4.1 OpenAIRE

OpenAIRE is an open and sustainable scholarly communication infrastructure responsible for the overall management, analysis, manipulation, provision, monitoring and cross-linking of all research outcomes (publications, related datasets, software and services) across existing, planned and future repositories. It has been supported by 3 EU funded projects (OpenAIRE2020 Project No 643410, OpenAIREplus Project n°: RI-283595 and OpenAIRE Project n°: RI-246686). OpenAIRE involves 50 partners from across the EU and uses its National Open Access Desks (NOADs) as representatives and liaisons in all EU member states and beyond.

The main service of OpenAIRE is to store and disseminate research publications and related material through Open Access policies. A multitude of services assists researchers to share their contributions online. OpenAIRE engages various stakeholders in the Open Access to science, which can roughly be categorized in the following groups: **The Repository Community, Research Funders, Research Data Initiatives and Infrastructures, European e-Infrastructures, Other Data/Research Initiatives, Open Access Initiatives and Organizations and Publishers and Publisher Organizations.**

Services

OpenAIRE offers services that facilitate Open Access to science to four major groups:

- **Researchers.** OpenAIRE helps researchers to share and retrieve publications and data. Authors are aided in finding a repository for their data, to link their publications to data or to funding sources, and to search through the published content.
- **Data providers.** Data providers are supported in enhancing the quality of their content by using tools that aggregate and transform data. Moreover, they are aided in monitoring the impact of their content from data usage statistics from OpenAIRE repositories.
- **Research Admins.** Research administrators can be informed for the EC policies on publications and they are aided in implementing them. They can quickly get an overview of their organization's content, especially for material related to EC projects and they can monitor their organization's Open Science output.
- **Funders.** Funders are aided in monitoring the results of their policies. OpenAIRE helps them to identify relationships among all research entities: publications, data, funding, researchers, organizations and data sources. Moreover, it allows performing advanced analytics based on topic modelling mechanisms.

Governance

OpenAIRE in its current form operates as a network of respective partners governed by the relevant Consortium Agreement. 50 partners, from all EU countries, and beyond, collaborate to work on this large-scale initiative that aims to promote open scholarship and substantially improve the discoverability and reusability of research publications and data. The initiative brings together professionals from research libraries, open scholarship organizations, national e-Infrastructure and data experts, IT and legal researchers, showcasing the truly collaborative nature of this pan-European endeavour. A network of

people, represented by the National Open Access Desks (NOADs), organises activities to collect H2020 project outputs, and support research data management.

Statistics

OpenAIRE provides access to around 20M publications and 45K datasets.

4.2 GEANT

GÉANT is a fundamental e-infrastructure in Europe, delivering the pan-European GÉANT network. Through its integrated catalogue of connectivity, collaboration and identity services, GÉANT provides users with highly reliable, unconstrained access to computing, analysis, storage, applications and other resources, to ensure that Europe remains at the forefront of research.

GEANT interconnects 38 National Research and Education Network (NREN) partners, and it is the largest and most advanced R&E network in the world. GEANT connects over 50 million users at 10,000 institutions across Europe and supporting all scientific disciplines. The backbone network operates at speeds of up to 500Gbps and reaches over 100 national networks worldwide.

Since its establishment over 20 years ago, the GÉANT network has developed progressively to ensure that European researchers lead international and global collaboration. Over 1000 terabytes of data are transferred via the GÉANT IP backbone every day. More than just an infrastructure for e-science, it stands as a positive example of European integration and collaboration.

GEANT develops and delivers advanced networks and associated e-infrastructure services. It supports open innovation, collaboration and knowledge-sharing amongst its members, partners and the wider research and education networking community.

Country	NREN	Country	NREN
Albania	ANA	Israel	IUCC
Algeria	ARN	Latvia	SigmaNet
Armenia	ASNET-AM	Lithuania	LITNET
Australia	AARNet	Luxembourg	RESTENA
Austria	ACOnet	Macedonia	MARnet
Azerbaijan	AzScienceNet	Moldova	RENAM
Belarus	BASNET	Montenegro	MREN
Belgium	Belnet	Morocco	MARWAN
Bosnia / Herzegovina	SARNET	Netherlands	SURFnet
Brazil	RNP	New Zealand	REANNZ
Bulgaria	BREN	Norway	UNINETT
Canada	CANARIE	Poland	PIONIER
Croatia	CARNet	Portugal	FCCN
Cyprus	CYNET	Romania	RoEduNet
Czech Republic	CESNET	Russian Federation	e-ARENA

Country	NREN	Country	NREN
Denmark	DeIC	Serbia	AMRES
Ecuador	CEDIA	Slovakia	SANET
Estonia	EENet	Slovenia	ARNES
Finland	FUNET	South Africa	SANREN
France	CNRS	Spain	RedIRIS
Georgia	GRENA	Sweden	SUNET
Germany	DFN	Switzerland	SWITCH
Greece	GRNET S.A.	Taiwan PoC	NCHC
Hungary	NIIF/HUNGARNET	Turkey	ULAKBIM
Iceland	RHnet	Ukraine	URAN
Ireland	HEAnet	United Kingdom	Jisc

Services

GEANT offers a multitude of services which can be categorized in the following groups:

- **Connectivity & network management.** Connectivity services support the NRENs in delivering world-class network facilities to the research and education community. These include GEANT IP, GEANT point-to-point services, GEANT Open, GEANT VPN services, GEANT Testbeds Services, eduroam, peftSONAR and eduPERT.
- **Trust, identity & security.** Securing access to services and providing federated identity systems to enable efficient collaboration. These include eduGAIN, eduroam, eduPKI, TCS, Trusted Introducer, TCAR, TRANSITS training and Federation as a Service.
- **Cloud services.** From large scale computing facilities to personalised storage, the cloud offers research and education immense opportunities. These include GEANT Cloud Services, FileSender and ownCloud.
- **Real-time communications.** Enabling communication and collaboration across the community. These include eduCONF, eduOER and NRERNum.net.
- **Professional services.** With more than 40 partners across Europe and a € multi-million budget, GEANT has met the challenge of complex international project management. GEANT provides consultancy on network related projects.

Governance

GEANT interconnects Europe's national research and education networking (NREN) organisations with award-winning high bandwidth, high speed and highly resilient pan-European backbone – connecting Europe's researchers, academics and students to each other, and linking them to over half the countries in the world.

GEANT's highest governing body is the General Assembly (GA), in which representatives of member organisations meet at least twice per year.

The GA elects members to the Board of Directors (BoD), which manages and administers the organisation. Day-to-day operations are carried out by the association's staff, based in Amsterdam and Cambridge, under the direction of the CEO and managers.

GEANT is an association under Dutch law, it has national members (one per state) and representative members (represent at least two legal entities of different countries), associate (no voting rights) and the possibility of establishing working committees.

Statistics

GEANT services a large number of users in 40 countries. According to the most recent report²³:

- In most of the 40 countries, more than 80% of the universities are connected to GEANT.
- 86% of all university-level students are serviced in those 40 countries; that is, a total of 25 million university students.
- GÉANT network reaches more than 50 million users involved in research and education in the region.
- The typical capacity for universities in GÉANT partner countries is now in the region of 10 Gb/s. All other user-categories have lower capacities, although research institutions are similar at 10 Gb/s.
- The 24 NRENs that have consistently submitted complete data, report traffic around 1700PB/year for the year 2015

4.3 PRACE

PRACE (Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe) offers a pan-European supercomputing infrastructure, providing access to computing and data management resources and services for large-scale scientific and engineering applications at the highest performance level.

PRACE aims to support all scientific disciplines that need high performance computing to achieve high impact discovery. In this sense it will enhance European competitiveness by offering world class computing and data management resources and services through a centralized peer review process.

The computer systems and their operations accessible through PRACE are provided by PRACE members. Four hosting members (BSC representing Spain, CINECA representing Italy, GCS representing Germany and GENCI representing France) secured funding for the initial period from 2010 to 2016. In 2017, PRACE has engaged in the second period of the Partnership, securing the operations of the infrastructure until 2020, and including a fifth Hosting Member, ETHZ representing Switzerland. During this second phase, PRACE will offer an initial performance above 62 Petaflops in 7 complementary leading edge systems, offering a total of 4.000 million core hours per year (75 million node hours). In pace with the needs of the scientific communities and technical developments, systems deployed by PRACE are continuously updated and upgraded to be at the apex of HPC technology. The following table summarises the current systems offered by PRACE:

System Name	Hosting Centre	Launch date	Architecture	Peak Performance
CURIE	GENCI@CEA, France	Q2 2011	Bull x86	2 Petaflops

²³ <https://compendium.geant.org/compendium-2015-updated.pdf>

System Name	Hosting Centre	Launch date	Architecture	Peak Performance
MARCONI	CINECA, Italy	Q3 2016	Lenovo NeXtScale	13 Petaflops
SuperMUC	GCS@LRZ, Germany	Q2 2012	IBM iDataPlex	6.4 Petaflops
JUQUEEN	GCS@FZJ, Germany	Q4 2012	IBM BlueGene/Q	5.87 Petaflops
MareNostrum	BSC, Spain	Q4 2012	IBM iDataPlex	1 Petaflops
Piz Daint	ETHZ, Switzerland	Q4 2016	Cray XC40/50	15.98 Petaflops
Hazel Hen	GCS@HLRS	Q4 2015	Cray XC40	7.42 Petaflops

The current phase of PRACE is a stepping stone towards a persistent and sustainable PRACE Research Infrastructure. Reducing the life-time cost of systems and their operations, the energy consumption of systems and the environmental impact is one of the goals of PRACE. PRACE undertakes similar software and hardware technology initiatives with the goal of preparing for changes in technologies used in the Research Infrastructure and provide the proper tools, education and training for the user communities to adapt to those changes. PRACE has further initiated the formation of STRATOS (STRAtegic TechnOlogies), an organization for collaboration with industry and other non-PRACE partner organizations. The PRACE leadership systems form the apex of resources for large-scale computing and data management for scientific discovery, engineering research and development for the benefit of Europe and are well integrated into the European HPC ecosystem.

The PRACE project partners receive EC funding under the PRACE Preparatory and Implementation Phase Projects (PRACE-PP, 2008-2010, RI-211528, PRACE-1IP, 2010-2012, RI-261557, PRACE-2IP, 2011-2013, RI-283493, PRACE-3IP, 2012-2017, RI-312763, PRACE-4IP, 2015-2017, 653838, PRACE-5IP, 2017-2019, 730913) for a total of €97 million complemented by the consortium budget of over €60 million.

Governance

PRACE is established as an international not-for-profit association (aisbl) with its seat in Brussels. It has 24 member countries whose representative organizations create a pan-European supercomputing infrastructure, providing access to computing and data management resources and services for large-scale scientific and engineering applications at the highest performance level. Working rules for all the following entities can be found in the PRACE web site (<http://www.prace-ri.eu/>).

The **Council** is the deliberative body of the Association and decides on all matters of the Association. It is composed of one representative from each Member. Depending on the nature of the decisions to be taken, different voting rules apply. As a general rule, decisions of a purely scientific nature are subject to majority vote, while decisions related to provisioning and usage of funding and resources require a qualified majority based on partner contributions. All other decisions require a double majority of members and contributions, apart from a small number of issues that imply changes in the contract of the Association which require unanimity. The Statutes of PRACE aisbl can be found on the PRACE web site (<http://www.prace-ri.eu/statutes>)

Board of the Council is elected by the Council from among the delegates representing the Members. It consists of a Chairman, a Vice-Chairman and a Secretary. The current members of the Board of the Council are: Anwar Osseyran (Chair), Sergi Girona (Vice- Chair) and Serge Bogaerts (Secretary).

The **Scientific Steering Committee (SSC)** is composed of European leading researchers that are responsible for advice and guidance on all matters of a scientific and technical nature which may influence the scientific work carried out by the use of the Association's resources. The SSC has an odd number of members up to a maximum of twenty-one, of which one is appointed Chairman. The members of the Scientific Steering Committee are appointed by the PRACE Council. SSC Members serve a two-year term renewable twice consecutively.

The **Access Committee (AC)** gives advice to the Board of Directors concerning the allocation of resources of the RI. The AC, proposed by the SSC, is composed of researchers experienced in areas of science, engineering and supercomputing. The AC is appointed by the Council and shall comprise an odd number of members with a minimum of five, from among which a Chairman and a Vice-Chairman are appointed. AC members serve a two year term renewable once.

The **Industrial Advisory Committee (IAC)** is composed of European industry representatives (both from multi-nationals and SMEs) representing 11 industrial sectors: Aeronautics/Aerospace, Automotive/Transport, Energy, Engineering/Manufacturing, Oil & Gas, Renewable Energy, Telecommunications/Electronics, ISV, HPC Vendors, Life Sciences, and Finances. They provide PRACE with advice on HPC usage for the benefit of European competitiveness and economic growth. The IAC reserves an observer seat for the Chair of ETP4HPC. A Chair and Vice-Chair are chosen by the committee, who, like all members, are appointed for 2 years renewable once.

The **Board of Directors (BoD)** is the executive body of the Association and is generally responsible for managing and representing the Association. The BoD is composed of a minimum of two members elected by the Council. Each Director will serve for an initial term of three years, renewable for subsequent periods of two years.

The PRACE RI has two forms of members:

Members – a government organization or legal entity representing a government. The PRACE RI accepts only one member per Member State of the European Union or of an associated country as described in article 217 of the European Union Treaty. Further, to be eligible as a PRACE RI member the legal entity must be responsible for the provisioning of HPC resources and associated services.

Hosting Members are members with the capacity to operate a Tier-0 HPC system and the commitment to contribute a fraction of its computing and data management resources to PRACE RI. There are five Hosting Members: France, Germany, Italy, Spain and Switzerland.

All partners contribute in cash or in-kind to the management of the RI and the delivery of services.

The PRACE Managing Director is responsible for the development of the strategy and vision for PRACE and the implementation of those as decided by the Council. The Managing Director is responsible for the delivery of PRACE services across Europe and management of the PRACE organisation.

The PRACE Peer Review process is one of the most critical functions of PRACE. It is governed by the Managing Director and managed by the PRACE RI staff. Applications for Project Access are subject to both technical feasibility evaluation and scientific peer review. The scientific peer review only assesses the scientific merit and expected European and International impact and ranks applications accordingly. The AC proposes to the Managing Director an allocation of PRACE resources based on the outcome of the technical and scientific peer review. Applications for Preparatory Access only undergo a technical

feasibility assessment. Project Access Calls for Proposals are issued twice a year. Preparatory Access can be requested at any time.

For delivery of computing and data management resources as well as many services the PRACE RI depends on hosting members as well as non-hosting members that have the necessary facilities, operations and maintenance staff and HPC expertise. Some of these activities are organized into EU Commission funded projects.

PRACE User Forum is not a body of the Association. It was set up in December 2011 through an initiative of PRACE itself. It is an independent entity where PRACE users can discuss their experiences and express their future needs as well as feedback on the current services and resources of the PRACE HPC Research Infrastructure. The aim is to provide an effective mechanism through which the Tier-0 user community can give feedback to PRACE.

The PRACE User Forum takes the outcomes of these discussions to PRACE on behalf of the User Community. The Forum has visibility in different social networks, such as [LinkedIn](#) and Twitter ([@PRACEuserforum](#)) on which all PRACE users are very welcome to start discussions and express their opinions.

Besides this online activity, the PRACE User Forum also organises one open session per year where users can voice their concerns, suggestions and issues in the presence of PRACE representatives.

Services

PRACE offers high performance computing resources to scientists and researchers from academia and industry from around the world through 2 forms of access:

- Preparatory Access is intended for short-term access to resources, for code-enabling and porting, required to prepare proposals for Project Access and to demonstrate the scalability of codes. Applications for Preparatory Access are accepted at any time. Applications for Preparatory Access undergo technical review only.
- Project Access is intended for individual researchers and research groups including multi-national research groups and can be used for 1-year as well as for 2-year or 3-year (Multi-Year Access) production runs. Project Access is subject to the PRACE Peer Review Process, which includes a technical and scientific review. Technical experts and leading scientists evaluate the proposals submitted in response to the bi-annual calls. Some calls are opened in collaboration with EUDAT to provide both computing and storage services at the same time.

PRACE is also offering training services to users, through PRACE Advanced Training Centre (PATC), PRACE Training Center (PTC), PRACE seasonal school and through online training material, including MOOCs. Some joint training is provided by PRACE and EUDAT.

PRACE is also using some services of GÉANT network e-infrastructure to provide access to its Tier-0 systems to European users.

Statistics

Figure 1 - PRACE usage per country – October 2016 (Source : <http://www.prace-ri.eu/statistics/>)

4.4 EGI

EGI is a federated e-Infrastructure set up to provide advanced computing services for research and innovation using grid computing techniques. The EGI e-infrastructure is publicly-funded and comprises over 300 data centres and cloud providers spread across 50 countries. EGI offers a wide range of services for compute, storage, data and support. Over the last two decades, EGI has notably been funded by national funding and by a series of EC research projects such as European DataGrid (2001-2004), Enabling Grids for E-sciencE (2004-2010), EGI-InSPIRE (2010-2014) and EGI-Engage (2014-2017).

EGI creates and delivers open solutions for science and research infrastructures by federating digital capabilities, resources and expertise between communities and across national boundaries. Researchers from all disciplines have easy, integrated and open access to the advanced scientific computing capabilities, resources and expertise needed to collaborate and to carry out data/compute intensive science and innovation.

Services

EGI delivers advanced data and computing services to support scientists, multinational projects and research infrastructures. The EGI Services are provided by EGI's federated cloud providers and data centres. The services can be requested by everyone involved in academic research and businesses and they can be categorized in the following groups:

■ Computing.

- **Cloud computing**, i.e., virtual machines on demand with complete control over computing resources.
- **Cloud Container Compute BETA**. Cloud Container Compute (in Beta phase) gives you the ability to deploy and scale Docker containers on-demand. It offers guaranteed computational resources in a secure and isolated environment with standard API access, without the overhead of managing the operating system. The result is improved performance, ideal for development work.
- **High-Throughput Compute**. Ability to execute thousands of computational tasks to analyse large datasets.

■ Storage and Data.

- **Online Storage**. EGI offers the ability to store, share and access your files and their metadata on a global scale.
- **Archive Storage**. Ability to back-up data for the long term and future use in a secure environment.
- **Data Transfer**. Ability to transfer large sets of data from one place to another.

■ Security

- **Check-in**. Ability to login with personal or home institution credentials.

■ Applications

- **Applications on Demand**. Ability to use online applications for data and compute intensive research.

■ Training.

- **FitSM training**. EGI offers training on how to manage IT services with a pragmatic and lightweight standard.
- **Training infrastructure**. Dedicated computing and storage for training and education.

- **ISO 27001 training.** EGI offers training on Information Security and how to implement a management system (ISMS)

Governance

The **EGI Foundation** (also known as **EGI.eu**) coordinates the EGI infrastructure on behalf of the participants of the EGI Council: national e-infrastructures and European Intergovernmental Research Organisations (EIROs).

The EGI Foundation is not-for-profit and was established in Amsterdam in 2010 under Dutch law. The foundation is led by Yannick Legré (Managing Director) and is governed by the EGI Council. Day-to-day operations are supervised by the Executive Board.

The EGI Council is responsible for defining the strategic direction of the EGI federation. The Council acts as the senior decision-making and supervisory authority of the [EGI Foundation](#), with a mandate to define the strategic direction of the entire EGI ecosystem.

The Council participants are organisations representing national e-infrastructures and two European Intergovernmental Research Organisations.

The EGI Council welcomes applications from like-minded organisations to become part of the EGI vision for a stronger research and innovation sector in Europe.

The EGI internal services are provided for the benefit of the [EGI Council](#) members and affiliated organisations.

The internal services complement the [EGI Services](#) for academia and business with tools designed to facilitate coordination and improve how the EGI Federation works together.

Statistics

EGI provides access to over 970,000 logical CPUs and 735 PB of disk and tape storage and delivers almost 4 Billion CPU hours per year to complete 562 Million jobs. More statistics are available at EGI portal²⁴.

4.5 EUDAT

EUDAT is a collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI), a common model and service infrastructure for managing data spanning all European research data centres and community data repositories. Its aim is to support sharing and preserving data across borders and disciplines.

European researchers and practitioners from any research discipline can preserve, find, access, and process data in a trusted environment, as part of the EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure a network of collaborating, cooperating centres, combining the richness of numerous generic and community-specific data repositories with the permanence and persistence of some of Europe's largest scientific data centres.

EUDAT offers heterogeneous research data management services and storage resources, supporting multiple research communities as well as individuals, through a geographically distributed, resilient network distributed across 15 European nations and data is stored alongside some of Europe's most powerful supercomputers. EUDAT is a Service-oriented, Community driven, Sustainable and Integrated initiative.

²⁴ <https://accounting.egi.eu/>

One of EUDAT's main ambitions is to bridge the gap between research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures through an active engagement strategy, using the communities that are in the consortium as EUDAT beacons and integrating others through innovative partnerships.

Services

EUDAT offers common data services, supporting multiple research communities as well as individuals, through a geographically distributed, resilient network of 36 European organisations. Its main services are the following:

- **B2DROP** is a secure and trusted data exchange service for researchers and scientists to keep their research data synchronized and up-to-date and to exchange with others.
- **B2SHARE** is a user-friendly, reliable and trustworthy way for researchers, scientific communities and scientists to store and share small-scale research data from diverse contexts.
- **B2SAFE** is a robust, safe and highly available service which allows community and departmental repositories to implement data management policies on research data across multiple administrative domains in a trustworthy manner.
- **B2STAGE** is a reliable, efficient, light-weight and easy-to-use service to transfer research data sets between EUDAT storage resources and high-performance computing (HPC) workspaces
- **B2FIND** is a simple, user-friendly metadata catalogue of research data collections stored in EUDAT data centres and other repositories.
- **B2HANDLE** provides an abstraction layer between a globally unique persistent identifier and a physical location of a data object allowing researchers to reliably cite and refer in the long term.
- **B2ACCESS** is an easy-to-use and secure authentication and authorization platform which can be integrated with any service and supports different methods of authentication.

Governance

- EUDAT had a dual governance structure. As an EU funded project, it operated through the respective bodies found in most EU projects, i.e. as defined by its Consortium Agreement. As an e-Infrastructure that provides a set of common data services EUDAT operates on the basis of the EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure.
- Generic and thematic service providers may join the EUDAT Collaborative data Infrastructure (CDI) network by signing a specific collaboration agreement.
- An EUDAT service provider and node can provide EUDAT CDI services to its (generic or thematic) user community of researchers. A service provider can join the EUDAT CDI either as an interoperable or an integrated node.

5 PARTICIPATION OF MEMBER STATE (MS) ORGANIZATIONS IN INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS

In this Section we explore the participation of MS organizations in previous infrastructure projects. We consider both e-Infrastructures and RIs. A complete list of the projects we consider appears in Annex A, together with every participating organization. The aim of the Section is to identify the most influential ones and further examine them in the next step of the scoping and mapping procedure. The data come from the CORDIS Portal (http://cordis.europa.eu/home_en.html), and the initial relevant project's list from the European Union Open Data Portal (<https://data.europa.eu/euodp/data/dataset/cordisref-data>). The classification of the organizations is done according to the self descriptions of activity types they provided in CORDIS.

The organizations with more than 10 participations appear in the following table.

Organization with more than 10 participations in EU Infrastructure projects		
Organization Name	No of Participation in EU Infrastructure	Activity type
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	61	Research Organisations
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	44	Research Organisations
COMMISSIONER ATOMIC ENERGY AND ALTERNATIVE ENERGY	37	Research Organisations
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL	31	Research Organisations
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	30	Research Organisations
STICHTING EGI	27	Other
MAX PLANCK GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV	25	Research Organisations
FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH	23	Other
EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	23	Research Organisations
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI FISICA NUCLEARE	20	Research Organisations
EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH	19	Research Organisations
BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	19	Research Organisations
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL	17	Research Organisations
LUNDS UNIVERSITET	16	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

Organization with more than 10 participations in EU Infrastructure projects		
GREEK RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY NETWORK S.A.	16	Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)
UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM	14	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	14	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIIKAN KESKUS OY	14	Other
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	13	Research Organisations
INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ PAN	13	Research Organisations
EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	12	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	12	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
STIFTUNG DEUTSCHES ELEKTRONEN-SYNCHROTRON DESY	12	Research Organisations
THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER	12	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	11	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	11	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	11	Research Organisations
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	10	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	10	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	10	Research Organisations

The participation of organizations in infrastructure projects by country is distributed as follows:

Participations in H2020 Infrastructure projects by country	
Country	No of Participations
Germany	332
United Kingdom	297
France	272
Italy	239
Netherlands	211
Spain	187
Greece	102
Sweden	83
Switzerland	81
Belgium	70
Finland	67
Norway	62
Poland	59
Czech Republic	54
Portugal	54
Austria	49
Hungary	46
Ireland	40
Denmark	37
Romania	31
Bulgaria	22
Slovenia	20
Israel	19
Russia	16
Slovakia	16
Serbia	14
Turkey	13
Estonia	12
Croatia	12
South Africa	10
Cyprus	9
Lithuania	9
Latvia	7
United States	7
Australia	6

Participations in H2020 Infrastructure projects by country	
Iceland	6
Bosnia and Herzegovina	6
Moldova	6
Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia	4
Malta	4
Montenegro	4
Armenia	4
Albania	3
Uruguay	3
Georgia	3
Ghana	3
Kenya	2
Canada	2
Belarus	2
Chile	2
Ukraine	2
India	2
Uganda	2
Jordan	2
Luxembourg	2
Germany	2
Mexico	1
Tunisia	1
Tanzania	1
Taiwan	1
South Korea	1
Brazil	1
Philippines	1
Nigeria	1
New Zealand	1
Japan	1
Colombia	1
Malaysia	1
Madagascar	1
Ecuador	1
Egypt	1
Kyrgyzstan	1
Indonesia	1
Grenada	1
China	1

The number of distinct participants per country is depicted in the following table:

Participants by Country	
Country	No of Participants
Germany	125
United Kingdom	103
France	98
Italy	92
Spain	84
Netherlands	70
Belgium	41
Greece	36
Poland	34
Norway	33
Hungary	32
Portugal	29
Czech Republic	27
Switzerland	26
Sweden	25
Austria	23
Finland	21
Ireland	21
Romania	20
Russia	14
Bulgaria	14
Denmark	14
Slovakia	13
Slovenia	10
Serbia	9
Turkey	8
Israel	8
Croatia	7
South Africa	7
United States	7
Bosnia and Herzegovina	5
Estonia	5
Cyprus	5
Iceland	4

Participants by Country	
Moldova	4
Latvia	4
Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia	3
Lithuania	3
Australia	3
India	2
Ukraine	2
Uganda	2
Armenia	2
Belarus	2
Montenegro	2
Kenya	2
Chile	2
Albania	2
Luxembourg	2
Canada	1
Ecuador	1
China	1
Egypt	1
Colombia	1
Brazil	1
Malaysia	1
Tunisia	1
Tanzania	1
Taiwan	1
South Korea	1
Philippines	1
Nigeria	1
New Zealand	1
Japan	1
Malta	1
Georgia	1
Magadascar	1
Kyrgyzstan	1
Uruguay	1
Jordan	1
Indonesia	1
Grenada	1
Ghana	1
Germany	1
Mexico	1

Participation in infrastructure projects shows a stakeholder landscape biased towards universities and research centres. The following graph and table show *the participations* by activity type in the projects.

Participations by Activity type	
Activity type	No of Participations
Research Organisations	1158
Higher or Secondary Education Establishments	894
Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)	212
Other	187
Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)	183

To get a better picture of the organizations that participate in the infrastructure projects, we present *participants* by Activity type in the following graph and table.

Participants by Type	
Activity type	No of Participants
Research Organisations	420
Higher or Secondary Education Establishments	366
Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)	153
Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)	106
Other	88

5.1 Analysis by country

In the following sections we analyse the participations of organizations according to their country of origin. Having a picture of the most influential organisations in each member state is essential, since important infrastructures and consumers operate at a national level. Apart from information about EU member states we also present data for Switzerland, due to its expensive participation in infrastructure projects.

5.1.1 Austria

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
BIOBANKS AND BIOMOLECULAR RESOURCES RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM (BBMRI-ERIC)	7	Research Organisations
OESTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN	5	Research Organisations
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT GRAZ	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITAT LINZ	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITAT WIEN	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UMWELTBUNDESAMT GMBH	4	Other
BUNDESMINISTERIUM FÜR WISSENSCHAFT, FORSCHUNG UND WIRTSCHAFT	3	Public bodies
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.2 Belgium

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
UNIVERSITEIT GENT	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE-EUROPEAN COMMISSION	5	Research Organisations
VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR DE ZEE VZW	4	Research Organisations

PARTNERSHIP FOR ADVANCED COMPUTING IN EUROPE AISBL	4	Other
FONDS VOOR WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK-VLAANDEREN	3	Research Organisations
SERVICE PUBLIC FEDERAL DE PROGRAMMATION POLITIQUE SCIENTIFIQUE	3	Public bodies
ASSOCIATION INTERNATIONALE EXTREME-LIGHT-INFRASTRUCTURE DELIVERY CONSORTIUM	3	Other
UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICRO-ELECTRONICA CENTRUM	2	Research Organisations
INSTITUT ROYAL DES SCIENCES NATURELLES DE BELGIQUE	2	Research Organisations
FONDS NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	2	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
EUROGOOS AISBL	2	Other
UNIVERSITEIT ANTWERPEN	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITE LIBRE DE BRUXELLES	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.3 Bulgaria

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
INSTITUTE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
INSTITUTE OF NUCLEAR RESEARCH AND NUCLEAR ENERGY - BULGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	3	Research Organisations
INSTITUTE OF MATHEMATICS AND INFORMATICS AT THE BULGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCE	2	Research Organisations
SOFIISKI UNIVERSITET SVETI KLIMENT OHRIDSKI	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ASSOCIATION "NATIONAL CENTRE FOR SUPERCOMPUTING APPLICATIONS"	2	Research Organisations

5.1.4 Croatia

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
RUDER BOSKOVIC INSTITUTE	6	Research Organisations
SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU SVEUCILISNI RACUNSKI CENTAR	1	Research Organisations
YOTTA ADVANCED COMPUTING DOO ZA ISTRAZIVANJE I USLUGE	1	Private for-profit entities
HRVATSKA AKADEMSKA I ISTRAZIVACKA MREZA CARNET	1	Research Organisations
FACULTY OF SCIENCE UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
Sveuciliste u Zagreb, GRAFICKI FAKULTET	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.5 Cyprus

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
European University Cyprus	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
KYPRIAKO EREVNITIKO KAI AKADIMAIKO DIKTYO	1	Research Organisations

5.1.6 Czech Republic

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
CESNET ZAJMOVE SDRUZENI PRAVNICKYCH OSOB	8	Research Organisations
FYZIKALNI USTAV AV CR V.V.I	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
USTAV MOLEKULARNI GENETIKY AKADEMIE VED CESKE REPUBLIKY VEREJNA VYZKUMNA INSTITUCE	4	Research Organisations
Masarykova univerzita	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
VYSOKA SKOLA BANSKA - TECHNICKA UNIVERZITA OSTRAVA	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
USTAV FYZIKY ATMOSFERY AV CR, v.v.i.	2	Research Organisations
MINISTRY OF EDUCATION YOUTH AND SPORTS	2	Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)

NUCLEAR PHYSICS INSTITUTE OF THE ASCR VVI	2	Research Organisations
MORAVSKA ZEMSKA KNIHOVNA V BRNE	2	Research Organisations
CENTRUM VYZKUMU GLOBALNI ZMENY AV CR VVI	2	Research Organisations

5.1.7 Denmark

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	10	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	10	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
AARHUS UNIVERSITET	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland	2	Research Organisations
SYDDANSK UNIVERSITET	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.8 Estonia

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
TARTU ULIKOOL	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
HARIDUS-JA TEADUS MINISTEERIUM	2	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)
HARIDUSE INFOTEHNOLOOGIA SIHTASUTUS	1	Other
AGILEWORKS OU	1	Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)
TARTU OBSERVATORY - ESTONIAN MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND RESEARCH	1	Research Organisations

5.1.9 Finland

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIIKAN KESKUS OY	14	Other
HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	12	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ILMATIETEEN LAITOS	8	Research Organisations
AALTO-KORKEAKOULUSAATIO	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
OULUN YLIOPISTO	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	3	Public bodies
SUOMEN YMPARISTOKESKUS	3	Research Organisations
ABO AKADEMI	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
JYVASKYLAN YLIOPISTO	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
TURUN YLIOPISTO	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.10 France

Participants with more than 5 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	61	Research Organisations
COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES	37	Research Organisations
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	13	Research Organisations
INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER	8	Research Organisations
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA SANTE ET DE LA RECHERCHE MEDICALE (INSERM)	7	Research Organisations
EUROPEAN SYNCHROTRON RADIATION FACILITY	6	Research Organisations
INSTITUT MAX VON LAUE - PAUL LANGEVIN	5	Research Organisations

5.1.11 Germany

Participants with more than 5 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
MAX PLANCK GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV	25	Research Organisations
FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH	23	Other
EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	23	Research Organisations
STIFTUNG DEUTSCHES ELEKTRONEN-SYNCHROTRON DESY	12	Research Organisations
FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	5	Research Organisations
Karlsruher Institut fuer Technologie	9	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER BILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG	9	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)
DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUER LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV	9	Research Organisations
GSI HELMHOLTZZENTRUM FUER SCHWERIONENFORSCHUNG GmbH	7	Research Organisations

UNIVERSITAET BREMEN	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGENSTIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN DEUTSCHES FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM FUER GESUNDHEIT UND UMWELT GMBH	6	Research Organisations
FORSCHUNGSVERBUND BERLIN EV	6	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITAET STUTTGART	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
FRAUNHOFER-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V	5	Research Organisations

5.1.12 Greece

Participants with more than 3 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
ETHNIKO DIKTYO EREVNAS TECHNOLOGIAS AE	16	Private for-profit entities
FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS	9	Research Organisations
HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH	8	Research Organisations
ATHENA RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CENTER IN INFORMATION COMMUNICATION & KNOWLEDGE TECHNOLOGIES	7	Research Organisations
GENIKI GRAMMATIA EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIAS	6	Public bodies
NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ETHNIKO IDRYMA EREVNON	5	Research Organisations
NATIONAL OBSERVATORY OF ATHENS	4	Research Organisations
AGRO-KNOW IKE	4	Private for-profit entities
INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	3	Research Organisations
ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.13 Hungary

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA WIGNER FIZIKAI KUTATOKOZPONT	5	Research Organisations
NEMZETI INFORMACIOS INFRASTRUKTURA FEJLESZTESI IRODA	5	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)
KORMANYZATI INFORMATIKAI FEJLESZTESI UGYNOKSEG	4	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)
Magyar Tudományos Akadémia Atommagkutató Intézete	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
SZILARDTESTFIZIKAI ES OPTIKAI KUTATOINTEZETE - MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA	2	Research Organisations
MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA SZAMITASTECHNIKAI ES AUTOMATIZALASI KUTATO INTEZET	2	Research Organisations

EOTVOS LORAND TUDOMANYEGYETEM	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
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5.1.14 Ireland

Participants with more than 2 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, GALWAY	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
MARINE INSTITUTE	5	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE PROVOST, FELLOWS, FOUNDATION SCHOLARS & THE OTHER MEMBERS OF BOARD OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY & UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE HEALTH RESEARCH BOARD	2	Public bodies
VEDURSTOFA ISLANDS	2	Research Organisations

SLR ENVIRONMENTAL CONSULTING(IRELAND)LIMITED	2	Private for-profit entities
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.15 Italy

Participants with more than 3 participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	44	Research Organisations
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI FISICA NUCLEARE	20	Research Organisations
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI GEOFISICA E VULCANOLOGIA	9	Research Organisations
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI ASTROFISICA	8	Research Organisations
CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO RISONANZE MAGNETICHE DI METALLO PROTEINE	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
AGENZIA NAZIONALE PER LE NUOVE TECNOLOGIE, L'ENERGIA E LO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO SOSTENIBILE	7	Research Organisations
CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO	7	Research Organisations
ELETTRA - SINCROTRONE TRIESTE SCPA	6	Research Organisations
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI OCEANOGRAFIA E DI GEOFISICA SPERIMENTALE	5	Research Organisations
AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA	4	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO-BICOCCA	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA	4	Private for-profit entities
CONSORZIO NAZIONALE INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER LE SCIENZE FISICHE DELLA MATERIA	3	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
CONSORTIUM GARR	3	Public bodies
PIN SOC.CONS. A R.L. - SERVIZI DIDATTICI E SCIENTIFICI PER L UNIVERSITA DI FIRENZE	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
STAZIONE ZOOLOGICA ANTON DOHRN	3	Research Organisations
FONDAZIONE CENTRO EURO-MEDITERRANEO SUI CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI	3	Research Organisations

5.1.16 Latvia

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATE	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATES AGENTURA LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATES BIOLOGIJAS INSTITUTS	1	Research Organisations
LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATES MATEMATIKAS UN INFORMATIKAS INSTITUTS	1	Research Organisations
LATVIJAS VALSTS KOKSNES KIMIJAS INSTITUTS	1	Research Organisations

5.1.17 Lithuania

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
VILNIAUS UNIVERSITETAS	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
VALSTYBINIS VILNIAUS GAONO ZYDU MUZIEJUS	1	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)

5.1.18 Luxembourg

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
Fondation RESTENA	1	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITE DU LUXEMBOURG	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.19 Malta

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
UNIVERSITA TA MALTA	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.20 Netherlands

Participants with 4 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	11	Research Organisations
STICHTING EGI	11	Other
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK	7	Research Organisations
STICHTING LIBER	6	Public bodies
UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
SURFSARA BV	6	Private for-profit entities
RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
SURFnet bv	5	Private for-profit entities
KONINKLIJK NEDERLANDS METEOROLOGISCH INSTITUUT-KNMI	5	Other

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	5	Research Organisations
ERASMUS UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM ROTTERDAM	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
STICHTING VU	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
VERENIGING VOOR CHRISTELIJK HOGER ONDERWIJS WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK EN PATIENTENZORG	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
GEANT VERENIGING	4	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.21 Poland

Participants with 2 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	13	Other
AKADEMIA GORNICZO-HUTNICZA IM. STANISLAWA STASZICA W KRAKOWIE	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIwersytet Warszawski	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
NARODOWE CENTRUM BADAN JADROWYCH	2	Research Organisations
Instytut Geofizyki Polskiej Akademii Nauk	2	Research Organisations
WOJSKOWA AKADEMIA TECHNICZNA IM JAROSLAWA DABROWSKIEGO	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
Wroclawskie Centrum Badan EIT+ Sp z o.o	2	Research Organisations

5.1.22 Portugal

Participants with 2 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
LABORATORIO DE INSTRUMENTACAO E FISICA EXPERIMENTAL DE PARTICULAS	5	Research Organisations
FUNDACAO PARA A CIENCIA E A TECNOLOGIA	5	Public bodies
UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
FUNDACAO DA FACULDADE DE CIENCIAS DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA FP	4	Research Organisations
CENTRO DE CIENCIAS DO MAR DO ALGARVE	4	Research Organisations
UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
LABORATORIO NACIONAL DE ENGENHARIA CIVIL	2	Research Organisations
INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
INSTITUTO DE CIENCIAS SOCIAIS DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ASSOCIACAO DO INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO PARA A INVESTIGACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	2	Research Organisations
FUNDACAO CALOUSTE GULBENKIAN	2	Research Organisations

5.1.23 Romania

Participants with 2 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
UNIVERSITATEA DIN BUCURESTI	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
"INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE -DEZVOLTARE PENTRU FIZICA SI INGINERIE NUCLEARA ""HORIA HULUBEI"" (IFIN-HH)"	4	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITATEA DE VEST DIN TIMISOARA	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU GEOLOGIE SI GEOECOLOGIE MARINA-GEOECOMAR	2	Research Organisations
INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE DEZVOLTARE PENTRU FIZICA LASERILOR PLASMEI SI RADIATIEI	2	Research Organisations
INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU FIZICA PAMANTULUI	2	Research Organisations

5.1.24 Slovakia

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
VYPOCTOVE STREDISKO SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED	2	Research Organisations
INSTITUTE OF LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY OF THE SLOVAK ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
MEDZINARODNE LASEROVE CENTRUM	2	Research Organisations
CENTRUM VEDECKO TECHNICKYCH INFORMACII SLOVENSKEJ REPUBLIKY	1	Public bodies
UNIVERZITA PAVLA JOZEFA SAFARIKA V KOSICIACH	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ZDRUZENIE POUZIVATELOV SLOVENSKEJAKADEMICKEJ DATOVEJ SIETE-SANET	1	Other
VIROLOGICKY USTAV SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED	1	Research Organisations
USTAV INFORMATIKY, SLOVENSKA AKADEMIA VIED	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERZITA KOMENSKÉHO V BRATISLAVE	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
SOCIOLOGICKY USTAV SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED	1	Research Organisations

JAZYKOVEDNY USTAV LUDOVITA STURA SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED	1	Research Organisations
DOKUMENTACNE STREDISKO HOLOKAUSTU OBCIANSKE ZDRUZENIE	1	Research Organisations
INSTITUTE FOR PUBLIC AFFAIRS	1	Public bodies

5.1.25 Slovenia

All participants		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ZNANSTVENORAZISKOVALNI CENTER SLOVENSKE AKADEMIJE ZNANOSTI IN UMETNOSTI	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN	3	Research Organisations
NARODNA IN UNIVERZITETNA KNJIZNICA	1	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)
UNIVERZA V NOVI GORICI	1	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
ARCTUR RACUNALNISKI INZENIRING DOO	1	Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)
INSTITUT ZA NOVEJSO ZGODOVINO	1	Research Organisations
INSTITUT ZA EKONOMSKA RAZISKOVANJA	1	Research Organisations
AKADEMSKA RAZISKOVALNA MREZA SLOVENIJE	1	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)

NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA BIOLOGIJO	1	Research Organisations
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5.1.26 Spain

Participants with 3 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	30	Research Organisations
BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	19	Research Organisations
CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES ENERGETICAS, MEDIOAMBIENTALES Y TECNOLOGICAS-CIEMAT	7	Research Organisations
FUNDACIO CENTRE DE REGULACIO GENOMICA	5	Research Organisations
INSTITUTO DE SALUD CARLOS III	5	Research Organisations
INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE TECNICA AEROSPAIAL ESTEBAN TERRADAS	5	Research Organisations
UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO EHU UPV	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA BIOMEDICA (IRB BARCELONA)	4	Research Organisations

UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
FUNDACION PARA EL DESAROLLO DE LA INVESTIGACION EN GENOMICA Y PROTEOMICA	3	Research Organisations
FUNDACION CENTRO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIONES ONCOLOGICAS CARLOS III	3	Research Organisations
UNIVERSIDAD DE CANTABRIA	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
CONSORCIO PARA LA CONSTRUCCION EQUIPAMIENTO Y EXPLOTACION DEL LABORATORIO DE LUZ SINCROTRON	3	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)
ATOS SPAIN SA	3	Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)
CONSORCIO PARA LA CONSTRUCCION, EQUIPAMIENTO Y EXPLOTACION DE LA SEDE ESPANOLA DE LA FUENTE EUROPEA DE NEUTRONES POR ESPALACION	3	Public bodies (excluding Research Organisations and Secondary or Higher Education Establishments)

5.1.27 Sweden

Participants with 2 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
LUNDS UNIVERSITET	16	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	11	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
VETENSKAPSRADET - SWEDISH RESEARCH COUNCIL	5	Public bodies
EISCAT SCIENTIFIC ASSOCIATION	5	Research Organisations
EUROPEAN SPALLATION SOURCE ESS AB	5	Research Organisations
GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET	4	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
CHALMERS TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLA AB	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
LINKOPINGS UNIVERSITET	3	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
FOLKHALSOMYNDIGHETEN	2	Research Organisations
SVERIGES METEOROLOGISKA OCH HYDROLOGISKA INSTITUT	2	Public bodies

5.1.28 Switzerland

Participants with 2 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH	19	Research Organisations
EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	12	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
PAUL SCHERRER INSTITUT	9	Research Organisations
ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITE DE GENEVE	6	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
SIB INSTITUT SUISSE DE BIOINFORMATIQUE	3	Research Organisations
EIDGENOSSISCHE MATERIALPRUFUNGS- UND FORSCHUNGSANSTALT	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITAET BERN	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITE DE LAUSANNE	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

SCHWEIZERISCHER NATIONALFONDS ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTLICHEN FORSCHUNG	2	Research Organisations
UNIVERSITAET ZUERICH	2	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

5.1.29 United Kingdom

Participants with 5 or more participations		
Organization name	No of Participations	Activity type
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL	31	Research Organisations
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL	17	Research Organisations
THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	14	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER	12	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	11	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	9	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
MEDICAL RESEARCH COUNCIL	8	Research Organisations
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE	8	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

CARDIFF UNIVERSITY	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL	7	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
GEANT LIMITED	5	Private for-profit entities (excluding Higher or Secondary Education Establishments)
THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ST ANDREWS	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
THE UNIVERSITY OF SHEFFIELD	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments
INSTRUCT ACADEMIC SERVICES LIMITED	5	Other
IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	5	Higher or Secondary Education Establishments

6 RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES BY SCIENTIFIC DOMAIN

A significant factor to better understand the stakeholder landscape is to take into account the scientific domain of existing infrastructure. We used the report on “Horizon 2020 and the Research Infrastructures Landscape”²⁵ to categorize the ESFRIs to the following domains:

- Environmental and Earth Sciences
- Biological and Medical Sciences
- Energy
- Material Sciences and Analytical Facilities
- Physical Sciences
- Social Science and Humanities
- Mathematics and ICT

Which are further broken down to the following areas:

Category	Domain
Atmosphere	Environmental and Earth Sciences
Biosphere	
Geosphere	
Hydrosphere Marine and Freshwater	
Hydrosphere Marine	
Biological Resource Centres	Biological and Medical Sciences
Genomics and Proteomics Facilities	
Imaging Facilities	
Medical Research Facilities	
Food and Agriculture Research Facilities	
Bioinformatics Resources	Energy
Energy	
Material Sciences and Analytical Facilities	Material Sciences and Analytical Facilities
Accelerators and Colliders	Physical Sciences
Astronomy	
Social Sciences	Social Science and Humanities
Arts and Humanities	
Linguistics	
Mathematics and ICT	Mathematics and ICT

The results are depicted in the following figures.

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/pdf/ri_landscape_2017.pdf

Infrastructure Projects by Scientific Field

Projects by Scientific Category

- Accelerators and Colliders
- Astronomy
- Bioinformatics Resources
- Biosphere
- Food and Agriculture Research Facilities
- Geosphere
- Hydrosphere Marine and Freshwater
- Interdisciplinary Platforms and Services
- Material Sciences and Analytical Facilities
- Medical Research Facilities
- Arts and Humanities
- Atmosphere
- Biological Resource Centres
- Energy
- Genomics and Proteomics Facilities
- Hydrosphere Marine
- Imaging Facilities
- Linguistics
- Mathematics and ICT

The distribution shows that RIs come from a wide range of scientific fields. Unlike e-infrastructures which are mostly ICT related, ICT RIs are only a minority here. This is a factor to consider, since sharing ICT services across geographical boundaries is relatively straightforward, but this is not always the case for non-ICT services.

7 QUESTIONNAIRE AND INTERVIEW DATA

The overview of participants in EU infrastructure projects we presented in Section 5 provided a broad picture of the stakeholder landscape, although it was naturally biased towards service providers, since they were the ones needing the most significant part of the funding. Service providers were mostly Universities and Research Institutions which, at the same time, act as users of infrastructures. This desk research gave us a first picture, but to have a better understanding of the stakeholder landscape we need also to take into account the views of the stakeholders themselves. To this end, we used questionnaires and interviews with selected stakeholders. The main aim of the questionnaires and interviews was to capture the awareness of stakeholders about EOSC, to get their own assessments as to how they view their role with respect to EOSC, their own expectations and priorities for EOSC and finally anything we might have missed in the statistical survey.

To better capture the different roles of stakeholders we avoided contacting universities and research organizations as independent entities, but instead we reached out to infrastructure and user organizations like GEANT, PRACE, EURODOC etc. This decision is supported by two other factors:

- the decision to build EOSC over existing infrastructures, which is supported both by the EOSC declaration²⁶ and by the EC working document SWD (2018) 83 final²⁷ “Implementation Roadmap for a European Open Science Cloud”.
- The fact the Research Institutions and Universities participate in infrastructure projects with different capacities, different roles, different departments and different research teams. Reaching out to any of these teams would capture a very partial view on EOSC.
- User organizations capture a broader community than universities and research institutions or, like EURODOC, they capture the view of user communities that are often under-represented in the respective organizations administration.

Questionnaires were filled out by persons deeply involved in the related organizations. Still, this was not an official response of the organization to our questions, but rather the view of individuals who often had key positions (e.g., head of the respective organization) or long experience working in the organization (e.g., senior researchers). We treat all responses as their personal views.

Data acquisition history

In the period from M3 to M21 where the refining phase of stakeholder mapping took place, EOSC matured and its vision became clearer. To capture this on-going involvement in EOSC maturity we got input from the stakeholders in multiple iterations, spread out in the whole reference period.

Documenting the stakeholders’ view was facilitated through questionnaires and occasionally interviews. The interviews were used to fill out the questionnaires we had prepared in advance. Questionnaires

²⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/eosc_declaration.pdf

²⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

evolved in each mapping phase based on our experience with the previous interviews and the evolution of the EOSC vision. The main objectives of the questionnaires were the following:

- **Descriptive information** about the interviewed organization. We were interested in categorizing the organizations as service providers or service consumers and in mapping interactions between big organizations, e.g., infrastructures, to possibly identify dependencies in service provision. Such goal quickly proved unrealistic. In fact, it required a lot of effort on the part of the interviewed and on the other such information would be collected only for a very small selected subset of stakeholders. The latter would not allow offering a meaningful picture of stakeholder interactions. Still, the statistical information that we collected provides a quantitative view on the impact on the stakeholder on the research community.
- **Adoption of FAIR principles.** Since the adoption of the FAIR principles in research is a goal for EOSC, the adherence to FAIR principles is an important indication for readiness of an organization to join the EOSC ecosystem. Moreover, even planning to implement procedures that comply with FAIR principles, is an indication of a positive attitude towards EOSC.
- **EOSC awareness.** The first interviews demonstrated that awareness about EOSC was limited. Not only EOSC scope and objectives were unclear to many stakeholders, but several were not aware of EOSC at all. We started to directly inquire about EOSC awareness at the later stages of the mapping process.
- **EOSC expectations.** Expectations from EOSC is one of the most important goals of reaching out to stakeholders via interviews and questionnaires. Whereas descriptive data and the activities of a stakeholder can be partially traced through desk research, the expectations (and sometimes the reservations) about EOSC can only be identified by direct inquiries.
- **Self-assessment of their role in EOSC.** It is important to capture how stakeholders imagine their own organization in the EOSC ecosystem and in the EOSC governance model. Whereas, we can place them according to their activities to different roles in the proposed EOSC governance architectures, it is meaningful to get their own views on how they assess their role in the research ecosystem.

Exploring the stakeholder landscape by reaching out to stakeholders to capture their views on EOSC, is closely intertwined with other outreaching activities of EOSCPilot like the stakeholder feedback on EOSC draft governance scheme of T2.5 and the feedback on policy recommendations that we collected in WP3. To increase synergies and reduce the strain on interviewed stakeholders, we often created common questionnaires and collected information both for the stakeholder mapping of D2.1 and other activities in a single interaction with the selected stakeholders.

7.1 History of information acquisition

The first interviews with stakeholders took place in the autumn of 2017 with some of them taking place on the side of Stakeholders Forum on the 28-29th of November 2017 in Brussels. The questionnaires used for these interviews were the 1st and the 2nd presented in Annex A.3.

The first interviews were done with individuals from PRACE, GEANT, GRNET, Eurodoc and DFG. PRACE and GEANT are EU e-Infrastructures that were described in Section 4, GRNET S.A. is a Greek public company responsible for support academic infrastructures, EURODoc is the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers and DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) is the self-governing organization for science and research in Germany. This selection covered several roles: 2 individuals from EU infrastructures (PRACE,GEANT), 1 from a national infrastructure (GRNET), 1 from a user association (EURODOC) and 1 from a funder (DFG). This first round was completed before at the initial steps of forming the EOSC vision and there was limited awareness of EOSC. Moreover, it showed some weaknesses of the questionnaires since rarely detailed information about statistics and services provided were available.

The second round of interviews took place in the context of receiving feedback for the draft policy recommendations in WP3, (D3.2). A common questionnaire was formed with those working on T3.2 with questions that contributed to both goals of D2.1 and D3.2. The focus in the interviews was on draft policy feedback, since it required a lot more detailed information compared to stakeholder mapping. The information provided by the interviewed in this round was very partial, so we do not present the results here.

After these two rounds we significantly restructured the questionnaire having in mind the three following goals: a) reduce its complexity and the questions collecting statistical data about the activities of the interviewed, b) take into account the lack of awareness for EOSC that was evident in interviews and several events and c) reflect the maturity of EOSC vision. This questionnaire was partially used in a joined questionnaire with T2.5, at SRCE e-Infrastructure Days 2018 in Croatia.

As a final step we approached and received input from COAR (Confederation of Open Access Repositories) and from EUA (European Universities Association), as these entities represent both a major stakeholder in open access data and one of the biggest user associations for EOSC. Moreover, the interviewees from GEANT, GRNET and Eurodoc provided us with updated information that we asked in the last version of the questionnaire. As a result, we present their information on the last round of interviews.

Several other efforts were made to approach more stakeholders, but unfortunately only a small percentage was able to respond.

7.2 Results

Due to the nature of the approach methodology (a mix of interviews and questionnaires) and the various version of questionnaires, not all responses from stakeholders are homogenous enough to present overall statistics. In this section, we first present some conclusions from each round of outreaching activities, and then we offer some overall findings based on all questionnaire versions.

Interview with an individual from PRACE.

PRACE is a service provider at EU level. It does not provide any data to other parties. PRACE is a non profit organization under Belgian law, that is governed by a high level council. Each member state appoints a delegate to the council. The council is the high level administration body that takes the important decisions. Other stakeholders interact through a user forum, which is not an official body.

PRACE is a major contributor to EU data infrastructure and. There was concern about the relation between PRACE and EOSC and the need for an efficient governance scheme for EOSC was stressed. (At the time, there was no proposal for the EOSC governance architecture).

Interview with and individual from DFG

DFG is a national funder in Germany. There is a concern on how EOSC will complement existing infrastructures and funding agencies. **DFG** believes that stakeholders should be engaged through existing associations and organizations.

Data from SRCE e-Infrastructure Days 2018

Data about stakeholders was collected in a joined effort with T2.5 at SRCE e-Infrastructure Days 2018²⁸ in Croatia. A questionnaire was filled by stakeholders who had attended a presentation about EOSC governance. The responses to the questions related to stakeholder mapping are shown in the following figures.

Figure 2 - Self description of stakeholders

²⁸ <https://www.srce.unizg.hr/en/news/srce-e-infrastructure-days-2018/publ2018-04-18>

Figure 3 - EOOSC Awareness

Figure 4 - EOOSC Expectations

The results come from 12 questionnaires. As we see in Figure 2 participants are split between service providers and end users. In Figure 3 we observe that awareness about EOOSC is low; 50% have never heard

it before and another 17% only knows of EOSC's existence. Finally, in Figure 4 we examine the stakeholders' expectations. 62% of them expect EOSC to focus on interoperability and 38% on strategic decisions that affect all infrastructures. No participant expects EOSC to help with joint purchase power. It should be noted, that the participants in this survey are not familiar with EOSC, and it is natural that they focus on the simplest tasks. When examining the data from individual questionnaires the expectations from EOSC are greater.

Interview with and individual from EURODOC

The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) is a non-profit organization based in Brussels which represents doctoral candidates and junior researchers in Europe. Eurodoc represents 32 national associations of doctoral candidates and junior researchers in Europe and is the de facto stakeholder for the 1+ million early-career researchers across Europe.

Eurodoc sees itself both as a consumer and a strategic stakeholder that will contribute to defining policies in EOSC. It sees the steering committee as a most suitable body for its participation in EOSC.

Eurodoc is positive towards FAIR principles, and towards following the EOSC rules of engagement. It is positive towards EOSC providing joint purchasing power to infrastructures and towards EOSC defining interoperability standards in technical and legal level. It reserves its opinion on the matter of having obligatory standards for infrastructures. Eurodoc stresses the need for EOSC to work in close collaboration with existing infrastructures and include them in decision making.

Interview with and individual from GEANT

GÉANT is the leading collaboration on the network and related infrastructure and services for the benefit of research and education. GÉANT has more than 50 million users of the 10.000 Academic Research and Education Institutions around Europe

GEANT sees itself both as provider and a strategic stakeholder that will contribute to defining policies in EOSC. It sees the both the strategic and the steering layer of EOSC as suitable bodies for participating.

GEANT plans to adopt FAIR principles, and it is positive towards following the EOSC rules of engagement. It agrees with EOSC providing joint purchasing power to infrastructures and towards EOSC defining interoperability standards in technical, legal, ethical and administrative level. It disagrees with obligatory standards for infrastructures. GEANT expects EOSC to organize its governance in such way that it will gain the trust of its stakeholders.

Interview with and individual from GRNET

GRNET S.A. is a Greek public company that operates under the auspices of the Greek Secretariat for Research and Technology / Ministry of Education, Research and Religious Affairs. GRNET provides Internet connectivity, high-quality e-Infrastructures and advanced services to the Greek Educational, Academic and Research community, aiming at minimizing the digital divide and at ensuring equal participation of its members in the global Society of Knowledge. Additionally, GRNET develops digital applications that ensure resource optimization for the Greek State, modernize public functional structures and procedures, and introduce new models of cooperation between public bodies, research and education communities, citizens and businesses. GRNET provides advanced services to the following sectors: Education, Research, Health, Culture.

GRNET has 213 connected members (all public R&E Institutions, Hospitals and other public not-for-profit) 9.000 km optical fibre network, 3 data centres, and it is the largest public cloud deployed in Greece with 500.000 daily users.

GRNET sees itself both as provider and a strategic stakeholder that will contribute to defining policies in EOSC. It sees the both the strategic and the steering layer of EOSC as suitable bodies for participating.

GRNET plans to adopt FAIR principles, and it is positive towards following the EOSC rules of engagement. It agrees with EOSC providing joint purchasing power to infrastructures and towards EOSC defining interoperability standards in technical, legal, ethical and administrative level. It disagrees with obligatory standards for infrastructures. GRNET expects EOSC to organize its governance in such way that it will gain the trust of its stakeholders.

Interview with and individual from COAR

COAR is an international association of repository initiatives. We work in several areas: capacity building, alignment and interoperability, a strategic voice for repositories, and next generation repositories. Over 140 members and partners from 36 countries on all 5 continents. Our members are universities, not-for-profit organizations and government agencies.

COAR sees itself as a strategic stakeholder that will contribute to defining policies in EOSC. It does not see itself having a role in EOSC governance bodies, since it is an international organization.

COAR considers FAIR principles a laudable goal, but most of its members' repositories are not mature enough to adopt them very soon. It agrees with EOSC defining interoperability standards in technical, legal and ethical level. It argues that standards should be obligatory or at least those that are mature and important enough. COAR considers EOSC as the organization that defines the requirements for greater interoperability and integration across services, that identifies gaps and that ensures reduced redundancy in service offerings in the European context.

Interview with and individual from EUA

The European University Association (EUA) is the representative organization of universities and national rectors' conferences in 47 European countries. EUA plays a crucial role in the Bologna Process and in influencing EU policies on higher education, research and innovation. EUA is made up of two different categories of members: institutional and individual members. Institutional members are National Rectors' Conferences from 32 different European countries. Individual members are universities in 47 countries across Europe totalling to more than 850 universities. More information on individual members is available through <http://www.eua.be/about/members-directory>.

EUA sees itself as a strategic stakeholder that will contribute to defining policies in EOSC. It sees itself contributing at the strategic level and it will encourage its member to participate in the steering level.

EUA promotes FAIR principles to each member. It agrees with EOSC defining interoperability standards in technical, legal, ethical and administrative level. It states that in some cases, to ensure effective interoperability at the EOSC-level, it may be necessary (e.g. through the rules of engagement) to select and impose certain constraints on which particular standards are supported in a given context. EUA argues that the promotion and adoption of standards by EOSC should be done in collaboration with relevant international organizations.

7.2.1 Summary of interviews key points

	GEANT	GRNET	EURODOC	COAR	EUA	Event in SRCE Days
With regards to EOsc would you consider your organization	Service provider and Strategic stakeholder	Service provider and Strategic stakeholder	Service consumer and Strategic stakeholder	Strategic Stakeholder	Strategic Stakeholder	-
What do you expect from EOsc	Positive towards joint purchase power. Expects to help with interoperability in all levels	Positive towards joint purchase power. Expects to help with interoperability in all levels	Positive towards joint purchase power. Expects to help with interoperability at the legal and technical level	To define interoperability requirements in technical, legal and ethical level	To define interoperability requirements in all levels	62% - To define interoperability standards 38% - Coordinate strategic decisions

In the above table we summarize the responses of the interviewees in the two most basic questions. We omit those for whom we did not have a direct response (these were interviewed in the very beginning of EOsc pilot). One result is that everyone sees itself as a strategic stakeholder (although this does not mean it expects to participate at the strategic level in the governance architecture). This reflects the eagerness of every stakeholder to participate in the decision taking for EOsc directions. Finally, the basic expectation of all stakeholders is that EOsc will increase interoperability amongst infrastructures and services.

8 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable we presented a view of the EOSC stakeholder landscape. We defined a methodology based on desk research followed by interaction with selected stakeholders, in the form of questionnaires and interviews. We presented the results of desk research on the most influential organizations in each country based on their participation in previous EC projects, considering both e-infrastructures and RIs. We identified several roles for stakeholders based on the different service layers and we also described 7 types of stakeholders: European e-Infrastructures, Data/Research Initiatives, Cloud providers, Research funders, Cloud community, Research Communities and Institutions, Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Policy makers.

We examined existing e-infrastructures, i.e., GEANT, EGI, PRACE, EUDAT, OpenAIRE, as we consider them a basic starting point for reviewing main stakeholders and governance models for EOSC. We presented their governance models, which provide important experience that can be exploited in defining the governance model for EOSC.

We went deeper into our analysis of stakeholders and we identified influential stakeholders in national and EU level, by analysing the participation of EU organizations in Horizon 2020 infrastructure projects (both e-infrastructures and Research Infrastructure projects) and in FP7 infrastructure projects. Our analysis is based on the number of participations of each organization in the infrastructure projects. We presented our results by activity type and also by a member state. This first analysis does not provide a complete and consistent mapping of the stakeholder landscape, but it enables EOSC to identify the best candidates for interviews, which is the next step in our scoping methodology. There are two main limitations of the existing analysis:

- Universities and research centres are over-represented. These types of organizations seek funding in EC projects more actively than companies or other public bodies and a picture of stakeholders that is based solely on participation in previous projects overestimates their impact in the research cloud ecosystem. Moreover, funders and policy makers usually do not participate in such projects and their importance is not revealed by such analysis.
- The stakeholder types we have identified and the types of organizations that are provided by the projects' descriptions do not much.

Despite its limitations, desk research provides an overview of the stakeholder landscape. Still, it lacks the view of the stakeholders themselves on EOSC and on the whole ecosystem. To capture this, we followed up the desk research with interviews and questionnaires. The results of this process revealed that the major expectation of stakeholders from EOSC is to promote interoperability and that all stakeholders would like to participate in strategic decisions.

The stakeholder mapping presented in this deliverable will enable EOSC to organize efficiently and fairly the its governance bodies as presented in EOSCPilot Deliverable 2.2. Whereas the main types of stakeholders that participate in each Governance layer stems from the responsibilities of each body, its internal organization (choosing the most suitable members, organizing the most representative sub-groups) depends on the actual stakeholder landscape. This deliverable will provide a solid basis for organizing each body and especially the steering layer, where most of the stakeholders will be represented.

ANNEX A.**A.1. H2020 and selected Fp7 Infrastructure projects**

Infrastructure Projects			
Code	Framework	Acronym	Call Identifier
654410	h2020	JERICO-NEXT	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
676627	h2020	ELITRANS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
675680	h2020	BlueBRIDGE	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654190	h2020	EUNCL	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
654110	h2020	HYDRALAB-PLUS	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
676621	h2020	IN-SKA	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
653982	h2020	GREST	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654124	h2020	SoNDe	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654248	h2020	CORBEL	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
675121	h2020	VI-SEEM	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
731001	h2020	AGINFRA PLUS	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1
654131	h2020	COOP_PLUS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654305	h2020	EuroCirCol	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654156	h2020	Rltrain	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654310	h2020	ODIP 2	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
676531	h2020	E-CAM	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
676536	h2020	SHARE-DEV3	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
676550	h2020	ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
643410	h2020	OpenAIRE2020	H2020-EINFRA-2014-1
654367	h2020	EarthServer-2	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
654139	h2020	LEARN	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
676580	h2020	NoMaD	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654206	h2020	TANDEM	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
731053	h2020	UBORA	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
690013	h2020	ORISON	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654359	h2020	eLTER	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
675419	h2020	EDISON	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
675728	h2020	BioExcel	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654384	h2020	ASCENT	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
654164	h2020	EHRI	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
654113	h2020	ERIGrid	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
653965	h2020	AARC	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
654166	h2020	CREMLIN	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
730913	h2020	PRACE-5IP	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1
654119	h2020	PARTHENOS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
675858	h2020	West-Life	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1

Infrastructure Projects			
654237	h2020	Sci-GaIA	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-2
675570	h2020	HaS-DARIAH	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
676541	h2020	OpenDreamKit	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654002	h2020	ENSAR2	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
646713	h2020	RICH	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-1
675191	h2020	ESIWACE	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
676564	h2020	EPOS IP	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
674943	h2020	READ	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654182	h2020	ENVRI PLUS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
676547	h2020	COEGSS	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
731102	h2020	HIRMEOS	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1
653493	h2020	Global BioImaging	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-2
674939	h2020	CESSDA-SaW	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
730941	h2020	AARC2	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1
654028	h2020	IPERION CH	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
689622	h2020	ERINHA2	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-2
654215	h2020	AHEAD	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
654003	h2020	GLOBIS-B	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-2
654404	h2020	B3Africa	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-2
676556	h2020	MuG	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
730974	h2020	RISCAPE	H2020-INFRADEV-2016-1
653980	h2020	ARISE2	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654148	h2020	LASERLAB-EUROPE	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
676247	h2020	VRE4EIC	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
676598	h2020	MaX	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
731063	h2020	MSO4SC	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1
674907	h2020	EVER-EST	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654371	h2020	ERIFORE	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
676555	h2020	EMSODEV	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
654225	h2020	MAGIC	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-2
653194	h2020	RDA Europe	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
676529	h2020	CLARIN-PLUS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
654220	h2020	EUCALL	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
676559	h2020	ELIXIR-EXCELERATE	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
653961	h2020	IPAD-MD	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-2
688945	h2020	EuBI PPII	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-2
676629	h2020	EoCoE	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654168	h2020	AIDA-2020	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
731031	h2020	OPERAS-D	H2020-INFRADEV-2016-1
653316	h2020	EVAg	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
654008	h2020	EMBRIC	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654039	h2020	THOR	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2

Infrastructure Projects			
675451	h2020	CompBioMed	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654416	h2020	SESAME NET	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
676134	h2020	CTA-DEV	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
730954	h2020	e-IRGSP5	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
654142	h2020	EGI-Engage	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
672008	h2020	EISCAT3D_PfP	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
654109	h2020	ACTRIS-2	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
731049	h2020	eInfraCentral	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
654024	h2020	SoBigData	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
689173	h2020	pp2EMBRC	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-2
730988	h2020	e-ROSA	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
689359	h2020	Quaco	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
653706	h2020	iNEXT	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
653477	h2020	ASTERICS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
676166	h2020	ESS-SUSTAIN	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
654241	h2020	PhenoMeNal	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
654065	h2020	EUDAT2020	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
653782	h2020	EuPRAXIA	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
652831	h2020	AQUAEXCEL2020	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
654296	h2020	MERIL-2	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654208	h2020	EPN2020-RI	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
730943	h2020	OPEN SESAME	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
731075	h2020	OpenRiskNet	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1
731011	h2020	OpenAIRE-Connect	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1
654280	h2020	RICHFIELDS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
676553	h2020	POP	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1
654021	h2020	OpenMinTeD	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
653549	h2020	INDIGO-DataCloud	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
654221	h2020	SERISS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
675206	h2020	ECCSEL	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
676548	h2020	BrightnESS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1
654387	h2020	RICAS2020	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
653838	h2020	PRACE-4IP	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2
654213	h2020	STR- ESFRI	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
654360	h2020	NFFA-Europe	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015
730928	h2020	InRoad	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
731016	h2020	AENEAS	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
731122	h2020	GN4-2	H2020-IBA-SGA-INFRA-GEANT-2016
654000	h2020	SINE2020	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1
777536	h2020	EOSC-hub	H2020-EINFRA-2017
739563	h2020	EOSCpilot	H2020-INFRADEV-2016-2

Infrastructure Projects			
687614	h2020	HNSciCloud	H2020-ICT-2015
730329	h2020	NextGEOSS	H2020-SC5-2016-OneStageB
823852	h2020	PaNOSC	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2
777367	h2020	XDC	H2020-EINFRA-2017
211753	fp7	METAFOR	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211338	fp7	SEE-GRID-SCI	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211804	fp7	EUFORIA	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212214	fp7	CESSDA-PPP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211252	fp7	INSTRUCT	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
206711	fp7	ILC-HIGRADE	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212073	fp7	GENESI-DR	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211597	fp7	EURO ARGO	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211796	fp7	ERICON-AB	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211528	fp7	PRACE	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211583	fp7	PREPARINGDARIAH	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211956	fp7	ETSF	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211714	fp7	NEUGRID	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
284443	fp7	EPPN	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2011-1
212147	fp7	DRIVER II	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211564	fp7	MNTEE	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211437	fp7	HPC-EUROPA++	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211909	fp7	SHARE-PREP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212105	fp7	ELI-PP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211737	fp7	HIPER	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211285	fp7	IRUVX-PP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212025	fp7	LASERLAB-EUROPE CONT	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211372	fp7	LIFEWATCH	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212128	fp7	IAGOS-ERI	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212104	fp7	EUROVO-AIDA	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211257	fp7	E-ELT PREP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211928	fp7	ERA-INSTRUMENTS	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211727	fp7	EDGES	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211938	fp7	MONDILEX	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211382	fp7	FAIR	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211404	fp7	INFRAFRONTIER	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
202914	fp7	NUPNET	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211738	fp7	ECRIN-PPI	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212111	fp7	BBMRI	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211693	fp7	EGI_DS	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211549	fp7	ESRFUP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212114	fp7	SLHC-PP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212057	fp7	ILL20/20	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1

Infrastructure Projects			
211810	fp7	PIREDEU	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211604	fp7	PRE-XFEL	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211816	fp7	EMSO	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211574	fp7	ICOS	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212205	fp7	COPAL	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211743	fp7	ET	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
202247	fp7	NEUTRONSOURCESS	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
211601	fp7	ELIXIR	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
212109	fp7	E-FAST	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2007-1
284209	fp7	BioMedBridges	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2011-1
283359	fp7	BioVeL	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2011-2
632694	fp7	CIVIC EPISTEMOLOGIES	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2013-2
610994	fp7	CloudWatch	FP7-ICT-2013-10
312274	fp7	DCH-RP	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2012-1- INFSO
261323	fp7	EGI-InSPIRE	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2010-2
283465	fp7	ENVRI	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2011-1

A.2. Participants in Infrastructure projects

Participant Name	No of Projects
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	61
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	44
COMMISSIONER AL ATOMIC ENERGY AND ALTERNATIVE ENERGY	37
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL	31
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	30
STICHTING EGI	11
MAX PLANCK GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV	25
FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH	23
EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	23
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI FISICA NUCLEARE	20
EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH	19
BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	19
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL	17
LUNDS UNIVERSITET	16
GREEK RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY NETWORK S.A.	16
UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM	14
THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	14
CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIKAN KESKUS OY	14
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	13
INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ PAN	13
EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	12
HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	12
STIFTUNG DEUTSCHES ELEKTRONEN-SYNCHROTRON DESY	12
THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER	12
UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	11
STICHTING EGI	11
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	11
KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	11
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	10
DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	10
FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	10
Karlsruher Institut fuer Technologie	9
PAUL SCHERRER INSTITUT	9
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	9
DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUER LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV	9
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI GEOFISICA E VULCANOLOGIA	9
BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER BILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG	9
FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS	9
HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH	8
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE	8
ILMATIETEEN LAITOS	8
CESNET ZAJMOVE SDRUZENI PRAVNICKYCH OSOB	8
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI ASTROFISICA	8

INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER	8
MEDICAL RESEARCH COUNCIL	8
TARTU ULIKOOL	7
CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO RISONANZE MAGNETICHE DI METALLO PROTEINE	7
CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES ENERGETICAS, MEDIOAMBIENTALES Y TECNOLOGICAS-CIEMAT	7
UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	7
CARDIFF UNIVERSITY	7
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA SANTE ET DE LA RECHERCHE MEDICALE (INSERM)	7
NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK	7
CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO	7
THE UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL	7
UNIVERSITAET BREMEN	7
BIOBANKS AND BIOMOLECULAR RESOURCES RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM (BBMRI-ERIC)	7
ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	7
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	7
AGENZIA NAZIONALE PER LE NUOVE TECNOLOGIE, L'ENERGIA E LO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO SOSTENIBILE	7
GSI HELMHOLTZZENTRUM FUER SCHWERIONENFORSCHUNG GmbH	7
NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	7
ATHENA RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CENTER IN INFORMATION COMMUNICATION & KNOWLEDGE TECHNOLOGIES	7
NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, GALWAY	6
EUROPEAN SYNCHROTRON RADIATION FACILITY	6
THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	6
KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN	6
NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	6
GENIKI GRAMMATIA EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIAS	6
UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	6
UNIVERSITE DE GENEVE	6
UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	6
UNIVERSITEIT GENT	6
FYZIKALNI USTAV AV CR V.V.I	6
KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET	6
GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGENSTIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	6
SURFSARA BV	6
UNIwersytet warszawski	6
ELETTRA - SINCROTRONE TRIESTE SCPA	6
AALTO-KORKEAKOULUSAATIO	6
STICHTING LIBER	6
AKADEMIA GORNICZO-HUTNICZA IM. STANISLAWA STASZICA W KRAKOWIE	6
HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN DEUTSCHES FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM FUER GESUNDHEIT UND UMWELT GMBH	6
RUDER BOSKOVIC INSTITUTE	6
FORSCHUNGSVERBUND BERLIN EV	6
VILNIAUS UNIVERSITETAS	6
KONINKLIJK NEDERLANDS METEOROLOGISCH INSTITUUT-KNMI	5
GEANT LIMITED	5
ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI OCEANOGRAFIA E DI GEOFISICA SPERIMENTALE	5
KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	5
VERENIGING VOOR CHRISTELIJK HOGER ONDERWIJS WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK EN PATIENTENZORG	5

INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE TECNICA AEROESPACIAL	5
OESTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN	5
MARINE INSTITUTE	5
EISCAT SCIENTIFIC ASSOCIATION	5
UNIVERSITAET STUTTGART	5
NEMZETI INFORMACIOS INFRASTRUKTURA FEJLESZTESI IRODA	5
INSTITUTO DE SALUD CARLOS III	5
EUROPEAN SPALLATION SOURCE ESS AB	5
LABORATORIO DE INSTRUMENTACAO E FISICA EXPERIMENTAL DE PARTICULAS	5
IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	5
MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA WIGNER FIZIKAI KUTATOKOZPONT	5
RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN	5
THE UNIVERSITY OF SHEFFIELD	5
FUNDACIO CENTRE DE REGULACIO GENOMICA	5
FUNDACAO PARA A CIENCIA E A TECNOLOGIA	5
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET EN AUTOMATIQUE	5
VETENSKAPSRADET - SWEDISH RESEARCH COUNCIL	5
ERASMUS UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM ROTTERDAM	5
STICHTING VU	5
THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ST ANDREWS	5
INSTITUT MAX VON LAUE - PAUL LANGEVIN	5
SURFnet bv	5
STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	5
STIFTELSEN SINTEF	5
INSTRUCT ACADEMIC SERVICES LIMITED	5
JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION	5
ETHNIKO IDRYMA EREVNON	5
INSTITUTE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES	4
WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	4
RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN	4
UNIVERSITETET I TROMSOE	4
LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATE	4
ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN	4
UNIVERSITAT LINZ	4
UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	4
VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR DE ZEE VZW	4
UNIVERSITA TA MALTA	4
VYSOKA SKOLA BANSKA - TECHNICKA UNIVERZITA OSTRAVA	4
"INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE -DEZVOLTARE PENTRU FIZICA SI INGINERIE NUCLEARA ""HORIA HULUBEI"" (IFIN-HH)"	4
FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA BIOMEDICA (IRB BARCELONA)	4
UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO-BICOCCA	4
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO	4
LUDWIG-MAXIMILIANS-UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	4
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	4
AARHUS UNIVERSITET	4
UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO	4
UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	4
GROUPEMENT D INTERET PUBLIC POUR LERESAU NATIONAL DE TELECOMMUNICATIONS POUR LA TECHNOLOGIE L ENSEIGNEMENT ET LA RECHERCHE	4
MACHBA - INTERUNIVERSITY COMPUTATION CENTER	4

THE UNIVERSITY OF READING	4
FUNDAÇÃO DA FACULDADE DE CIÊNCIAS DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA FP	4
INFRAFRONTIER GMBH	4
HERMANN VON HELMHOLTZ-GEMEINSCHAFT DEUTSCHER FORSCHUNGSZENTREN EV	4
UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO EHU UPV	4
UMWELTBUNDESAMT GMBH	4
GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITÄT HANNOVER	4
COMMONWEALTH SCIENTIFIC AND INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH ORGANISATION	4
AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA	4
UNIVERSITÄT WIEN	4
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITÄT GRAZ	4
UNIVERSITATEA DIN BUCUREȘTI	4
AGRO-KNOW IKE	4
JACOBS UNIVERSITY BREMEN GMBH	4
CENTRE EUROPEEN DE RECHERCHE ET DE FORMATION AVANCEE EN CALCUL SCIENTIFIQUE	4
SYNCHROTRON SOLEIL SOCIÉTÉ CIVILE	4
THE UNIVERSITY OF NOTTINGHAM	4
TRUST-IT SERVICES LIMITED	4
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GEANT VERENIGING	4
KORMANYZATI INFORMATIKAI FEJLESZTESI ÜGYNÖKSÉG	4
ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA	4
THE UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM	4
THE PROVOST, FELLOWS, FOUNDATION SCHOLARS & THE OTHER MEMBERS OF BOARD OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY & UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN	4
NATIONAL OBSERVATORY OF ATHENS	4
UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN	4
MET OFFICE	4
PARTNERSHIP FOR ADVANCED COMPUTING IN EUROPE AISBL	4
CENTRO DE CIÊNCIAS DO MAR DO ALGARVE	4
UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	4
USTAV MOLEKULÁRNÍ GENETIKY AKADEMIE VĚD ČESKÉ REPUBLIKY VEŘEJNÁ VÝZKUMNÁ INSTITUCE	4
UNIVERSITY OF YORK	4
Masarykova univerzita	4
FONDAZIONE CENTRO EURO-MEDITERRANEO SUI CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI	3
THE HEBREW UNIVERSITY OF JERUSALEM	3
THE UBUNTUNET ALLIANCE FOR RESEARCH AND EDUCATION NETWORKING	3
METEO-FRANCE	3
FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE	3
SIB INSTITUT SUISSE DE BIOINFORMATIQUE	3
THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	3
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT	3
CONSORZIO NAZIONALE INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER LE SCIENZE FISICHE DELLA MATERIA	3
PIN SOC.CONS. A R.L. - SERVIZI DIDATTICI E SCIENTIFICI PER L UNIVERSITÀ DI FIRENZE	3
COOPERACION LATINOAMERICANA DE REDES AVANZADAS	3
STICHTING SURF	3
RANNSOKNAMIDSTOD ISLANDS	3
COUNCIL FOR SCIENTIFIC AND INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH	3
NORSK INSTITUTT FOR LUFTFORSKNING	3
STICHTING KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT BRABANT UNIVERSITEIT VAN TILBURG	3
CONSORTIUM GARR	3

RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL NETWORKING ASSOCIATION OF MOLDOVA	3
RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN	3
STICHTING ASTRON, NETHERLANDS INSTITUTE FOR RADIO ASTRONOMY	3
ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK	3
STAZIONE ZOOLOGICA ANTON DOHRN	3
RUPRECHT-KARLS-UNIVERSITAET HEIDELBERG	3
EBERHARD KARLS UNIVERSITAET TUEBINGEN	3
STICHTING NEDERLANDSE WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK INSTITUTEN	3
SERVICE PUBLIC FEDERAL DE PROGRAMMATION POLITIQUE SCIENTIFIQUE	3
CESSDA AS	3
CHALMERS TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLA AB	3
TEL AVIV UNIVERSITY	3
Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	3
CLARIN ERIC	3
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	3
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	3
SUOMEN YMPARISTOKESKUS	3
EUROPEAN SOCIAL SURVEY EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM	3
OULUN YLIOPISTO	3
EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM FOR THE SURVEY OF HEALTH, AGEING AND RETIREMENT IN EUROPE	3
DIGITAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE ARTS AND HUMANITIES	3
EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS	3
Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	3
CONSORCIO PARA LA CONSTRUCCION EQUIPAMIENTO Y EXPLOTACION DEL LABORATORIO DE LUZ SINCROTRON	3
CONSORCIO PARA LA CONSTRUCCION, EQUIPAMIENTO Y EXPLOTACION DE LA SEDE ESPANOLA DE LA FUENTE EUROPEA DE NEUTRONES POR ESPALACION	3
CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE	3
EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY	3
JOINT INSTITUTE FOR V.L.B.I. IN EUROPE (J.I.V.E.)	3
LINKOPINGS UNIVERSITET	3
UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	3
UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE	3
JAVNA USTANOVA UNIVERZITET CRNE GORE PODGORICA	3
ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	3
JISC LBG	3
UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE	3
ASSOCIATION INTERNATIONALE EXTREME-LIGHT-INFRASTRUCTURE DELIVERY CONSORTIUM	3
HAVFORSKNINGSINSTITUTTET	3
GEORGIAN RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL NETWORKING ASSOCIATION	3
ATOS SPAIN SA	3
GENOME RESEARCH LIMITED	3
UNIVERSITATEA DE VEST DIN TIMISOARA	3
FUNDACION PARA EL DESAROLLO DE LA INVESTIGACION EN GENOMICA Y PROTEOMICA	3
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	3
FUNDACION CENTRO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIONES ONCOLOGICAS CARLOS III	3
JOHANNES GUTENBERG-UNIVERSITAT MAINZ	3
INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	3
INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN	3
ZNANSTVENORAZISKOVALNI CENTER SLOVENSKE AKADEMIJE ZNANOSTI IN UMETNOSTI	3

INSTITUT PASTEUR	3
INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT	3
INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATICS AND AUTOMATION PROBLEMS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA	3
ABO AKADEMI	3
ISTANBUL TEKNIK UNIVERSITESI	3
WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	3
GESIS - LEIBNIZ INSTITUT FUR SOZIALWISSENSCHAFTEN e.V.	3
VEREIN ZUR FOERDERUNG EINES DEUTSCHEN FORSCHUNGSNETZES DFN VEREIN E.V.	3
INSTITUTE OF NUCLEAR RESEARCH AND NUCLEAR ENERGY - BULGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	3
UNIVERZITET U BEOGRADU	3
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM GEESTHACHT ZENTRUM FUR MATERIAL- UND KUSTENFORSCHUNG GMBH	3
UNIVERSITY OF STRATHCLYDE	3
UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	3
UNIVERSITY OF GLASGOW	3
WEST AND CENTRAL AFRICAN RESEARCH AND EDUCATION NETWORK	3
BUNDESMINISTERIUM FÜR WISSENSCHAFT, FORSCHUNG UND WIRTSCHAFT	3
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA	3
TURKIYE BILIMSEL VE TEKNOLOJIK ARASTIRMA KURUMU	3
UNINETT SIGMA2 AS	3
MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA SZAMITASTECHNIKAI ES AUTOMATIZALASI KUTATO INTEZET	3
UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	3
MARINE BIOLOGICAL ASSOCIATION OF THE UNITED KINGDOM	3
CENTRE EUROPEEN DE RECHERCHE EN BIOLOGIE ET MEDECINE	3
UNIVERSIDAD DE CANTABRIA	3
MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	3
FREIE UNIVERSITAET BERLIN	3
BIOTECHNOLOGY AND BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES RESEARCH COUNCIL	3
CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE RECHERCHE SUR LE CANCER	3
FONDS VOOR WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK-VLAANDEREN	3
INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO	2
MINISTERE DE L'EDUCATION NATIONALE, DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT SUPERIEUR ET DE LA RECHERCHE	2
INSTITUTO ESPANOL DE OCEANOGRAFIA	2
INSTITUTO DE FISICA DE ALTAS ENERGIAS	2
INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE DEZVOLTARE PENTRU FIZICA LASERILOR PLASMEI SI RADIATIEI	2
INSTITUTO DE CIENCIAS SOCIAIS DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA	2
INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU GEOLOGIE SI GEOECOLOGIE MARINA-GEOECOMAR	2
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUER INFektionsFORSCHUNG GMBH	2
PROVINCIA LOMBARDO VENETA ORDINE OSPEDALIERO DI SAN GIOVANNI DI DIO - FATEBENEFRAPELLI	2
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM DRESDEN-ROSSENDORF EV	2
ENVISCOPE GMBH, MESSTECHNIK FUER UMWELTFORSCHUNG	2
FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER	2
POLITECNICO DI MILANO	2
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM BERLIN FUR MATERIALIEN UND ENERGIE GMBH	2
Instytut Geofizyki Polskiej Akademii Nauk	2
INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU FIZICA PAMANTULUI	2
INSTITUT TEORETICHESKOI I EKSPERIMENTALNOI FIZIKI ITEP	2
SIGMA ORIONIS SA	2
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE L ENVIRONNEMENT ET DES RISQUES INERIS	2
MEDZINARODNE LASEROVE CENTRUM	2

SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE	2
SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE	2
SCUOLA IMT (ISTITUZIONI, MERCATI, TECNOLOGIE) ALTI STUDI DI LUCCA	2
FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATIONS FAO	2
SCHWEIZERISCHER NATIONALFONDS ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTLICHEN FORSCHUNG	2
INSTITUTE OF MATHEMATICS AND INFORMATICS AT THE BULGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCE	2
INSTITUT ROYAL DES SCIENCES NATURELLES DE BELGIQUE	2
EIDGENOSSISCHE MATERIALPRUFUNGS- UND FORSCHUNGSANSTALT	2
INSTITUT ZA FIZIKU	2
ROBERT KOCH-INSTITUT	2
INSTITUTE OF APPLIED PHYSICS, RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	2
MINISTERIO DE CIENCIA E INNOVACION	2
INSTITUTE OF LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY OF THE SLOVAK ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	2
EOTVOS LORAND TUDOMANYEGYETEM	2
MARIENE INFORMATIE SERVICE MARIS BV	2
METEOROLOGICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL EARTH OBSERVATION SRL	2
EATRIS ERIC	2
LABORATORIO EUROPEO DI SPETTROSCOPIE NON LINEARI	2
HEINRICH-HEINE-UNIVERSITAET DUESSELDORF	2
JYVASKYLAN YLIOPISTO	2
Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland	2
KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS	2
MAAT FRANCE SARL	2
EUROPEAN SOUTHERN OBSERVATORY - ESO EUROPEAN ORGANISATION FOR ASTRONOMICAL RESEARCH IN THE SOUTHERN HEMISPHERE	2
GEIE ERCIM	2
Gauss Centre for Supercomputing (GCS) e.V.	2
KONSORTIUM DEUTSCHE MEERESFORSCHUNG e.V.	2
NUCLEAR PHYSICS INSTITUTE OF THE ASCR VVI	2
FUNDACION PUBLICA GALLEGA CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DE SUPERCOMPUTACION DE GALICIA	2
EUROPEAN X-RAY FREE-ELECTRON LASERFACILITY GMBH	2
LABORATORIO NACIONAL DE ENGENHARIA CIVIL	2
FUNDACIO INSTITUT CATALA DE NANOCIENCIA I NANOTECNOLOGIA	2
NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO	2
FUNDACION ESPANOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA	2
FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE CIENCIES FOTONIQUES	2
LEIBNIZ INSTITUT FUER TROPSPHAERENFORSCHUNG e.V.	2
LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT DSMZ-DEUTSCHE SAMMLUNG VON MIKROORGANISMEN UND ZELLKULTUREN GMBH	2
NATURAL HISTORY MUSEUM	2
NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION	2
FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	2
EURO-ARGO ERIC	2
MINISTERIE VAN ONDERWIJS, CULTUUR EN WETENSCHAP	2
JISC COLLECTIONS AND JANET LIMITED	2
HEALTHGRID	2
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STIFTUNG ZUR WISSENSCHAFTLICHEN ERFORSCHUNG DER ZEITGESCHICHTE - INSTITUT FUR ZEITGESCHICHTE IFZ	1
STIFTUNG PREUSSISCHER KULTURBESITZ	1
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INSTITUTO DE ASTROFISICA DE CANARIAS	1
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INSTITUTE OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY AND BIOCHEMISTRY OF THE ASCR VVI	1
INSTITUTE OF OCEANOLOGY - BULGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	1
INSTITUTE OF HUMAN VIROLOGY NIGERIA LTDGTE	1
INSTITUTO HIDROGRAFICO	1
Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry PAS	1
INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE SAUDE DR. RICARDO JORGE	1
INSTITUTE FOR PUBLIC AFFAIRS	1
INSTITUTE FOR PARALLEL PROCESSING OF THE BULGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	1

INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TRANSMISSION PROBLEMS RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES IITP	1
INSTITUT ZA NOVEJSO ZGODOVINO	1
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International Prevention Research Institute SAS	1
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MEO-SERVICOS DE COMUNICACOES E MULTIMEDIA SA	1
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MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA SZEGEDI BIOLOGIAI KOZPONT ENZIMOLOGIAI INTEZET	1
MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA OKOLOGIAI KUTATOKOZPONT	1
MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA GEODEZIAI ES GEOFIZIKAI KUTATOINTEZET	1
MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA ENERGIATUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT	1
MAX-DELBRUCK-CENTRUM FUR MOLEKULARE MEDIZIN IN DER HELMHOLTZ-GEMEINSCHAFT	1
NARODNA IN UNIVERZITETNA KNJIZNICA	1
NEMZETI AGRARKUTATASI ES INNOVACIOSKOZPONT	1
NEDERLANDSE FEDERATIE VAN UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRA	1
NATURHISTORISKA RIKSMUSEET	1
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NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS - NTUA	1
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NARODOHOSPODARSKY USTAV AKADEMIE VED CESKE REPUBLIKY VEREJNA VYZKUMNA INSTITUCE	1
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MUSEUM NATIONAL D'HISTOIRE NATURELLE	1
MUSEUM AND INSTITUTE OF ZOOLOGY - POLISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	1
Museo Nacional del Prado	1
MTA OKOLOGIAI ES BOTANIKAI KUTATOINTEZETE	1
MONTANUNIVERSITAT LOBEN	1
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MOLECULAR MEDICINE IRELAND LBG	1
MITTUNIVERSITETET	1
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A.3. Questionnaires

First version of the questionnaire

- 1) Please describe your institution.
- 2) Does your organisation provide services:
 - (a) At national level
 - (b) At EU level
 - (c) At international level
- 3) Does your organisation provide services to third parties? Please indicate the services type and the most important third parties
 - a) Basic cloud
 - b) Data services
 - c) High performance computing
 - d) Networking
 - e) Skills/ Training/ Support
- 4) Does your institution consume services from third parties? Please indicate the services type and the most important third parties
 - a) Basic cloud
 - b) Data services
 - c) High performance computing
 - d) Networking
 - e) Skills/ Training/ Support
- 5) Does your institution provide data to third parties? Please describe the data and the main third parties.
- 6) Does your institution consume data from third parties? Please describe the data and the main third parties.
- 7) To what extent are the data provided by your organization compliant with the FAIR principles:
 - a) Findable (Y/N)
 - b) Accessible (Y/N)
 - c) Interoperable (Y/N)
 - d) Reusable (Y/N)
- 8) Are you offering services to a specific research community (e.g. health sciences, humanities) or are your services horizontal/ interdisciplinary
- 9) Do you have any type of statistics for your institution as a consumer or a provider of services? E.g.,
 - a) Number of persons and organizations that consume services of your institution
 - b) Number of persons and organizations that provide services to your institution
 - c) Statistics about research funded by your institution
 - d) Any other statistic which depicts the impact of your institution in research

- 10) Does your institution act as policy maker for research? Please elaborate
- 11) Does your institution fund research? Please elaborate
- 12) What is the legal form of your institution?
- 13) Do you have any collaborations for service provision? Please include the main ones
- At national level
 - At EU level
 - At international level
- 14) Please indicate the types of stakeholders (if any) participating to your governance body
- 15) Please indicate if any users/ stakeholders were/ are involved in the co-development of the services
- 16) Please indicate your relations with other stakeholders
- 17) Are the services offered part of a National Research Infrastructure or e-Infrastructure roadmap?
- 18) How are the services funded?
- National Funds on a regular basis
 - National Funds on a project basis
 - EU funds on a project basis
 - Co-funded on a project basis
 - Other (describe)
- 19) What is the role of your organization in the context of a National Data Services plan (if any)?
- 20) Please indicate any stakeholder you deem important for EOSCPilot and it is not related to existing ESFRIs or e-Infrastructures.
- On national level:
 - Data/Research Initiatives
 - Cloud providers
 - Research funders.
 - Cloud community.
 - Research Communities and Institutions.
 - National Infrastructures
 - Policy makers.
 - Any other international

Second version of the questionnaire

- 21) Please describe your institution.
- 22) Does your organisation provide services:
- At national level
 - At EU level
 - At international level
- 23) Does your organisation provide services to third parties? Please indicate the services type and the most important third parties
- Basic cloud

- b) Data services
 - c) High performance computing
 - d) Networking
 - e) Skills/ Training/ Support
- 24) Does your institution consume services from third parties? Please indicate the services type and the most important third parties
- a) Basic cloud
 - b) Data services
 - c) High performance computing
 - d) Networking
 - e) Skills/ Training/ Support
- 25) Does your institution provide data to third parties? Please describe the data and the main third parties.
- 26) Does your institution consume data from third parties? Please describe the data and the main third parties.
- 27) To what extent are the data provided by your organization compliant with the FAIR principles:
- a) Findable (Y/N)
 - b) Accessible (Y/N)
 - c) Interoperable (Y/N)
 - d) Reusable (Y/N)
- 28) Are you offering services to a specific research community (e.g. health sciences, humanities) or are your services horizontal/ interdisciplinary
- 29) Do you have any type of statistics for your institution as a consumer or a provider of services? E.g.,
- a) Number of persons and organizations that consume services of your institution
 - b) Number of persons and organizations that provide services to your institution
 - c) Statistics about research funded by your institution
 - d) Any other statistic which depicts the impact of your institution in research
- 30) Does your institution act as policy maker for research? Please elaborate
- 31) Does your institution fund research? Please elaborate
- 32) What is the legal form of your institution?
- 33) How do you envisage your role in EOSC?
- 34) Please indicate any stakeholder you deem important for EOSCPilot and it is not related to existing ESFRIs or e-Infrastructures.
- a) On national level:
 - i) Data/Research Initiatives
 - ii) Cloud providers
 - iii) Research funders.

- iv) Cloud community.
 - v) Research Communities and Institutions.
 - vi) National Infrastructures
 - vii) Policy makers.
 - b) Any other international
- 35) Do you have any suggestion on the governance model for EOSC?

Third version of the questionnaire (final)

About EOOSC and EOSCPilot

The European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC) aims to accelerate and support the current transition to more effective Open Science and Open Innovation in the Digital Single Market. EOOSC introduces the idea of commons based on scientific data. EOOSC will facilitate systematic and professional data management and long-term stewardship of scientific data assets and services in Europe and globally. In the context of EOSCPilot project we aim to establish a governance framework for the EOOSC and contribute to the development of European open science policy and best practice. To this end EOSCPilot has proposed a 3-tier governance model with the following layers:

The proposed EOOSC Governance model has three basic layers

- **Strategic.** The strategic layer is populated by the EU institutions (member states, the EC) and it is responsible for articulating the strategic objectives for the EOOSC, and the metrics to measure how well the EOOSC delivers against these objectives.
- **Executive.** The Executive layer is responsible that the needs of the stakeholders are met through the strategic objectives set by the Institutional layer.
- **Steering.** The Steering layer consists of the Stakeholder Forum which represents the interests of Stakeholder Roles of Consumers, Providers, and Intermediaries. The Steering layer determines best practice, standards and principles of engagement.

1. Please describe briefly your organization
2. Please provide some statistics about your activities, e.g., number of members, number of consumers you service.
3. Please indicate the main funding sources for your organization.
4. Do you know about EOSC?
 - a. No
 - b. I've only heard it exists
 - c. Yes
 - d. I am involved in EOSC related projects
5. With regards to EOSC would you consider your organization
 - a. Provider, i.e., your organization will provide services in the EOSC ecosystem
 - b. Consumer, i.e., your organization will consume services from the EOSC ecosystem
 - c. Strategic stakeholder, i.e., your organization is a funder or an entity that will define policies for the EOSC ecosystem
6. If you are a service provider do you offer services:
 - a. To a specific scientific community (if so please indicate the scientific field)
 - b. Horizontal services for every scientific community
7. Do you receive funding for from infrastructure projects?
8. Do you fund infrastructure projects?
9. What do you expect from EOSC;
 - a. Should EOSC coordinate/align/define strategic decisions about EU infrastructures that run across e-Infras and RIs?
 - b. Should it help EU infrastructures to have a joint purchasing power?
 - c. Should it provide interoperability standards for services of EU infrastructures? At what level?
 - i. Technical
 - ii. Legal
 - iii. Ethical
 - iv. Administrative
 - d. Should it impose them?
10. Would you follow EOSC service compliance principles (or rules of engagement)?
11. Do you know about FAIR principles? Do you follow them? Do you plan to follow them?
12. Do you intend to offer open data in the EOSC ecosystem?

ANNEX B. GLOSSARY

Term	Explanation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ECI	European Cloud Initiative
EDI	European Data Infrastructure
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
PRACE	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe